

Ecological and Socioeconomic Baseline Studies to Support Gazettement of Two Proposed Marine Conservation Areas (MCAs) in Pemba East

WCS Tanzania

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Ministry of Blue Economy and Fisheries
of the Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar

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Contents

List of Abbreviations	6
1 Socioeconomic Surveys	13
1.1 Socio-Economic Profile and Basic Necessities Survey	13
1.1.1 Introduction	13
1.1.2 Methodology	13
1.1.3 Results	15
1.2 Climate-Change Risk Assessment	24
1.2.1 Introduction and Methodology	24
1.2.2 Results	25
1.2.3 Discussion	28
2 Ecological Surveys	30
2.1 Benthic Ecological Surveys (BES)	30
2.1.1 Introduction	30
2.1.2 Methodology	31
2.1.3 Results	34
2.1.4 Conclusions	44
2.2 Coral Reef Monitoring	46
2.2.1 Introduction	46
2.2.2 Methodology	46
2.2.3 Results	48
2.2.4 Conclusions	53
2.3 Mangrove Ecosystem Surveys	55
2.3.1 Introduction	55
2.3.2 Methodology	55
2.3.3 Results	60
2.3.4 Conclusions	66
2.4 Fisheries Catch and Landing Site Monitoring	67
2.4.1 Introduction	67
2.4.2 Bony Fish Landings Monitoring Methods	67
2.4.3 Sharks and Rays Landings Monitoring Methods	68
2.4.4 Baited Remote Underwater Video (BRUV)	69

2.4.5	Results	70
2.4.6	Conclusions	75
2.5	Fishery Pattern Mapping (FPM)	79
2.5.1	Introduction	79
2.5.2	Methods	79
2.5.3	Results	83
2.5.4	Conclusions	90

List of Abbreviations

AGB Above Ground Biomass

AGC Above Ground Carbon

AI Artificial Intelligence

BES Benthic Ecological Survey

BGB Below Ground Biomass

BGC Below Ground Carbon

BMU Beach Management Unit

BNS Basic Necessities Survey

BRUV Baited Remote Underwater Video

CRA Climate Risk Assessment

CRS Climate Risk Score

DFO District Fisheries Officer

DMC Department of Marine Conservation

Doria Patrols (local term for enforcement patrols)

FPM Fishery Pattern Mapping

HH Household

LIT Line Intercept Transect

MCA Marine Conservation Area

MoBEF Ministry of Fisheries and Blue Economy

MPA Marine Protected Area

SES Socio-Economic Survey

SFC Shehia Fisheries Committee

USAID United States Agency for International Development

UVC Underwater Fish Visual Census

VU Vulnerable (IUCN Red List status)

WCS Wildlife Conservation Society

WIO Western Indian Ocean

WIOMN Western Indian Ocean Mangrove Network

Executive Summary

This section provides high-level summaries of each section in this report, highlighting the key findings and outcomes.

Socio-Economic and Basic Necessities Surveys

A baseline socio-economic survey (SES) and Basic Necessities Survey (BNS) were conducted in 32 Shehias in Pemba East in 2024. The surveys covered aspects related to well-being, livelihoods, threats from climate change, and attitude towards marine conservation.

- Demographics:** Of the respondents, 50.74% were female and 49.25% were male, with a mean age of 56.33 years. The heads of their respective households comprised 57.07% of the respondents. The oldest age group, 65+, had the lowest representation (9.78%), while the 25–34 age group had the largest (23.74%). This implies that a significant percentage of young adults starting their families and jobs were successfully included in the study. 1.58% of respondents had finished post-secondary education, whereas the majority (43.13%) had not finished primary school.
- Livelihoods:** Out of 1,074 respondents, 49.9% were fishers, with men constituting 74.25% of fishers. Women showed interest in seaweed farming (38.1%). A potential conservation challenge noted was the usage of seine nets with small mesh sizes (<3”) by 11.0% of fishers. Alternative Livelihood Interest (Top 5): The highest interests for diversification were Crop Farming (554 respondents), Chicken/Duck Raising (488), Fish farming (483), and Seaweed farming (454).
- Basic Necessity Score (BNS):** The overall BNS score for East Pemba was 65%. Fishing-related households (66%) had a higher well-being score than non-fishing-related households (62%), a finding unique to this seascape. Key gaps related to livelihood opportunities, food, electricity, and education.
- Management Measures:** The most overwhelming management need expressed was strengthening enforcement through Doria (Patrols) (63.50% requested). Respondents also supported permanent and temporary closures (51.60%) and gear restrictions (45.30%).

Climate Risk Assessment Summary

A Climate Risk Assessment (CRA) was conducted using SES and BNS data, using a novel approach to integrate data from perception on occurrence and vulnerability from climate threats and the impact that climate related events can have on communities based on their level of wellbeing.

- *High-Risk Villages (Top 10)*: The villages in Pemba North and Pemba South with the highest climate risk scores were: Chamboni, Kojani, Shanake, Kiungoni, Msuka Mashariki, Msuka Magharibi, Tumbe Magharibi, Tumbe Mashariki, Mjini Wingwi, and Kinowe.
- *Observed Threats*: Over 70% of households in Pemba observed changes in heat and rains, winds, and water temperature. Changes in heat, rains, and winds were the most common threats reported as affecting livelihoods. In Kojani, 86% reported observing coastal erosion and 71% reported flooding.

Benthic Ecological Surveys (BES)

The survey employed a novel, cost-effective methodology to survey benthic substrates in shallow waters. The method used photoquadrats collected from a small boat to sample 413 stations at depths up to 50 meters, gathering over 1,239 photo quadrats.

Key Ecological Findings

- **Landscape Composition**: The seafloor is dominated by sand (46.7%) and fleshy algae (15.8%), with high-value habitats like coral and seagrass occupying less than 15% of the total area.
- **Seagrass Dominance**: Seagrass is the most prevalent high-value habitat (29.7% of the area), forming large, continuous meadows primarily in sheltered, shallow lagoons at depths of 0–12 meters.
- **Rare Coral "Hotspots"**: Hard coral is comparatively rare, covering only 7.8% of the surveyed area. These communities are "shelf-edge specialists," localized in narrow bands at depths of 15–25 meters. Exceptional "coral gardens" with >50% cover are extremely restricted, representing less than 1% of the coastline.

Coral Reef Monitoring Summary

Coral reef baseline data were collected at sites in Pemba East. Surveys included pre- and post-bleaching surveys, benthic substrate surveys, fish abundance and biomass surveys and recruitment surveys at selected locations. All data is available on datamermaid.org.

- *Coral Cover*: The 2024 bleaching event caused significant coral loss. At Vumawimbi reef, cover dropped from $37.5 \pm 4.7\%$ pre-bleaching to $18.5 \pm 0.4\%$ post-bleaching. At Kojani reef, cover dropped from 35.5 ± 3.1 pre-bleaching to 6.75 ± 0.2 post-bleaching.
- *Fish Biomass*: Fish biomass was highest at Vumawimbi reef (924 ± 24 kg/ha) and Furaha reef (504 ± 147 kg/ha), with Vumawimbi's high biomass attributed to its community closure management regime. Biomass was lowest at Mshame Outer South reef (15.43 ± 4.99 kg/ha) and Kukuu reef (95 ± 17 kg/ha). Shamiani and Kukuu were below the threshold of 300 kg/ha.
- *Sea Urchin Density*: Sea urchin density was highest at Kojani site (52 urchin/10m² or 14 ± 6 urchin/10m²) and lowest at Vumawimbi reef (zero observed) and Chambani reef (3 ± 1 urchin/10m²).

Mangrove Forest Survey

Mangrove Resource Assessment was conducted in 2025 by WIOMN to provide a baseline for restoration planning. Data was collected on above and below biomass to support blue carbon calculations on mitigation effects.

- *Species and Structure*: Pemba exhibited high species richness (8 species). Species were dominated by *Avicennia marina* (40%) and *Rhizophora mucronata* (30%). Structural values (stem density, basal area) were low relative to global and regional reference values, suggesting recovery from past degradation. The inverted J-shape diameter distribution indicated a regenerating population structure.
- *Biomass and Carbon*: Pemba's total biomass was 109.97 Mg ha⁻¹ (AGB 31.51 Mg ha⁻¹), and Above Ground Carbon (AGC) was 50.59 Mg C ha⁻¹. These values are lower than expected ranges (150 - 300 Mg ha⁻¹) for healthy mangrove forests.
- *Degradation*: Sites were highly degraded, with Tumbe being the most degraded, recording up to 3,775 stumps/ha. The degradation is driven by wood extraction for poles and charcoal, fish-bait excavation (polychaete worms), soil destabilization from these activities, and agricultural expansion (rice farming).
- *Regeneration*: High seedling densities were observed for *R. mucronata* and *A. marina* in Kinowe and Mjananza. However, the ratio showed poor transition from seedlings to saplings.

- *Cover Change*: Mangrove area in Pemba declined from 3,324.9 ha (1990) to 2,605.5 ha (2023), a net loss of 22%. The annual loss averaged 0.6% and accelerated to 3.1% over the past decade.
- *Restoration Strategy*: Due to high degradation in Pemba, direct planting and active restoration are recommended strategies to rapidly re-establish forest structure. Ten priority areas for targeted mangrove restoration were mapped.

Surveys on Bony Fishes and Elasmobranchs

Data collectors have been recording data on landings of bony fishes and elasmobranchs at four landings sites in Pemba East October 2023. Data on sharks and rays is analyzed at the species level and integrated with results from recent BRUV survey.

Bony Fish Landings

Fisheries catch data were collected from October 2023 to October 2025 at four landing sites in Pemba East: Msuka, Mtangani, Mvumoni Furaha, and Kojani.

- *Catch Totals*: Monitoring recorded a total of 2,589 trips with a total catch of 37,451.73 kg.
- *Vessels and Gear*: Landings were dominated by fiberglass boats and canoes. The most frequently recorded gear types were long line (long), traps, and ring nets.
- *Species Group*: Reef fish and small pelagics dominated landings at most sites, though tuna-like species dominated Mtangani.

Sharks and Rays (Chondrichthyan) Landings

Data on sharks and rays (chondrichthyans) were collected via market surveys at landing sites and Baited Remote Underwater Video (BRUV) surveys.

- *Landings Surveys*: Data collected from October 2023 to October 2025 recorded 253 records of 5 landed species. Top landings included the Round ribbontail ray (*Taeniurops meyeri*, listed as Vulnerable (VU) on the IUCN Red List).
- *BRUV Surveys*: A total of 95 BRUV samplings were conducted in Pemba. This ecological data helps assess coastal shark populations and identify "hotspots".

Fishers Pattern Mapping Summary

A Fishery Patterns Mapping (FPM) survey was conducted in 2024 to map location of fishing grounds for the communities in Pemba East. The survey was used to determine areas with large fishing pressure and the behaviour of fishers in different seasons and for different gears.

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- *Effort Distribution:* Fishing effort is concentrated along the reef edge in the northern part of Pemba East, especially near Musuka, with much less activity in the southeastern area.
 - *Fishing Gear Effort:* Handlines, longlines, and spears account for most of the effort, with traps contributing somewhat.
 - *Fishing Grounds Scale:* Most fishing grounds are relatively small in scale, but longlines, shark nets, and ring nets operate over the largest areas. Gears like spears and traps are associated with the smallest grounds (less than 25 km^2).
 - *Seasonality:* During the Kusi monsoon, fishing effort shifts from the eastern side to the western side of the islands, as strong winds affect fishing grounds for small vessels.
 - *Closures:* Most fishing grounds along the northern, eastern, and southern coasts of Pemba East were recommended for temporary closure, with only a few proposed for permanent closure.

Chapter 1

Socioeconomic Surveys

1.1 Socio-Economic Profile and Basic Necessities Survey

1.1.1 Introduction

The Pemba East proposed conservation area is essential for supporting coastal community livelihoods, which depend on marine resources for food security, income, and cultural practices. Primary livelihood activities include traditional fishing, tourism, and small-scale agriculture. Understanding community well-being, household demographics, and livelihoods is critical for the successful establishment of the new Marine Conservation Area. This section examines key challenges facing coastal communities, including declining fish catches, climate change impacts, marine resource degradation, and gender-based differences in access to resources.

WCS and Mwambao conducted baseline socioeconomic surveys across all 32 identified Shehias along Pemba's east coast. To reduce costs and resource requirements, two surveys were combined into a single data collection effort. The Socio-Economic Survey (SES) gathered information on respondents' livelihoods, observations of climate change threats, perceptions of climate change impacts on livelihoods, perceptions of marine ecosystem degradation, interest in alternative livelihoods, and perceptions of marine protected areas (MPAs) and their enforcement. The Basic Necessities Survey (BNS) assessed household-level well-being by documenting access to community-identified material goods and services. Together, these surveys provide critical insights into the economic drivers and conditions of communities where the Blue Action Fund Project operates.

1.1.2 Methodology

Survey questionnaires contained both open-ended and closed-ended questions, which enumerators entered directly into the KoboToolbox mobile application. All field teams received comprehensive training on data collection procedures, ethical survey protocols, and culturally sensitive approaches to sensitive topics. Respondents were explicitly informed of their right to refuse participation or withdraw from the survey at any time. To ensure a representative sample and minimize bias, we employed random household sampling, targeting approximately 40 households per village across all villages in Pemba East.

Figure 1.1: Survey team interviewing community member in Pemba

Socio-economic surveys

The Socio-Economic Survey (SES) was designed to collect key demographic information about households in the project area. It collected data on household composition, primary livelihoods, educational attainment, perceptions of climate change impacts and threats, and interest in alternative livelihood opportunities.

Basic Necessities Score

The Basic Necessities Survey (BNS) assesses household well-being by identifying community-defined essential items and services. Unlike externally imposed measures, the BNS recognizes that perceptions of necessity vary within and across communities, making it locally relevant. This methodology follows WCS's Guide 2.0 to the Basic Necessities Survey [Detoef et al., 2020] and has been successfully implemented in over 20 countries across Africa, Asia, and Latin America.

Survey Design The BNS questionnaire collects data on household access to essential goods and services: clean water, livelihood opportunities, electricity, healthcare, education, household items, and primary livelihood activities. Households identified which items and services they consider necessary for daily life, producing a well-being score grounded in local context and values rather than external assumptions. This approach is cost-effective, ethically sound, and provides an affordable way to assess community economic status.

Methodology Data collection was facilitated using Kobo Toolbox on smartphones. For each item or service, households provided a percentage value indicating perceived necessity. An item or service with a value exceeding 50% was classified as a necessity required to sustain life. Notably, most surveyed villages considered most of the listed items and services essential to their daily survival.

Data Analysis Households were categorized into two groups: fishing-related and non-fishing-related livelihoods. Overall BNS scores and regional scores were calculated using WCS's standard methodology to represent the well-being and vulnerability of each surveyed community.

1.1.3 Results

The results were generated from surveys conducted in 2024 by WCS and Mwambao. For the Socio-Economic Survey, WCS surveyed 475 households and Mwambao surveyed 277 households for a total of 752 households surveyed across 22 villages. The BNS survey covered a larger sample because it was conducted across two projects. A total of 873 households were surveyed by WCS, and 181 by Mwambao, for a total of 1054 households across 24 villages. The total number of surveyed households per village and survey is listed in Table 1.1, and the percentage of total households (HH) surveyed in each village for each survey type is also shown. The survey was designed to provide a statistically significant representation of the communities in Pemba East. Considering a total of approximately 29,000 households (HH) in the whole of Pemba East (as per 2022 census data), the current sampling effort of 873 HH for the SES and 1054 HH for the BNS is well above the required 380 HH to achieve a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error, which is considered statistically sufficient for the purposes of this baseline report. The survey results are presented in the following sections, beginning with the socio-economic survey, followed by the basic necessities survey.

Livelihood sources, challenges, opportunities, and needs

The BNS survey includes a question on the primary livelihood of the respondents, which is important for understanding the economic drivers of the communities in Pemba East. Respondents are asked to list the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th livelihoods as important in their household. The results show that the most common primary livelihood is "Other Crop/Fruit/Vegetable Farming" (347 respondents), followed by "Fishing" (262 respondents) and "Other (Specify)" (118 respondents). The distribution of livelihoods across the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th categories is shown in Table 1.2 below. This table provides insights into the diversity of livelihood activities among the respondents and highlights the importance of agriculture and fishing as primary sources of income for many households in Pemba East. These results are in line with other studies that show the strong dependence of coastal communities to marine resources in Tanzania [Allen, 2017] and how this can affect their ability to cope with creation of MPAs [Desbureaux et al., 2024].

The community's economic landscape is heavily anchored in *Other Crop, Fruit, and Vegetable Farming*, which is the most significant primary livelihood, with 347 households ranking it first. *Fishing* follows as the second most dominant primary activity (262 households), though its frequency drops sharply in the lower rankings, suggesting it is a specialized primary trade rather than a supplemental one.

Table 1.1: Demographic data across various villages.

Village name	SES	BNS	Total pop	HH	HH % SES	HH % BNS
Chambani	38	40	6096	1088.57	3%	4%
Dodo	21	none	4268	762.14	3%	none
Kangagani	21	40	3135	559.82	4%	7%
Kengeja (Chole)	42	36	6967	1244.11	3%	3%
Kibokoni (Vitongoji)	14	41	2584	461.43	3%	9%
Kinowe	64	59	4380	782.14	8%	8%
Kiungoni	21	51	3112	555.71	4%	9%
Kiuyu mbuyuni (Shenake)	59	59	6416	1145.71	5%	5%
Kiwani	21	31	3026	540.36	4%	6%
Kojani (Mpambani)	29	38	2358	421.07	7%	9%
Majenzi	57	60	2370	423.21	13%	14%
Mchakwe	21	none	3005	536.61	4%	none
Msuka (Mashariki / Magharibi)	80	40	8534	1523.93	5%	3%
Mtangani	21	40	3198	571.07	4%	7%
Mtemani	20	40	3017	538.75	4%	7%
Muambe (Mchakwe, Bwegeza)	42	41	6662	1189.64	4%	3%
Mvumoni (Furaha)	21	40	2463	439.82	5%	9%
Shanake	10	none	4237	756.61	1%	none
Shumba mjini	56	61	4763	850.54	7%	7%
Sizini	60	60	5284	943.57	6%	6%
Vitongoji	14	none	4517	806.61	2%	none
Wingwi Njuguni	20	41	3518	628.21	3%	7%

Interestingly, while some activities, such as *Poultry Farming* and *Livestock Keeping*, have modest numbers as first choices, they exhibit high prevalence as secondary livelihoods (68 and 60 households, respectively), indicating that they serve as vital "buffer" industries to supplement primary income. Conversely, specialized maritime activities such as *Seaweed Farming* show a strong primary presence (115 households) but taper off significantly, ranking fourth. Emerging or niche sectors such as *Crab Fattening*, *Sponge Farming*, and *Salt Making* remain marginal across all rankings, accounting for only a fraction of the community's economic engagement relative to the traditional pillars of agriculture and capture fisheries.

To compare the economic activities, the livelihoods have been categorized into *Marine Related* (including *Fishing*, *Seaweed Farming*, *Fish Trading*, etc.) and *Non-Marine Related* (including *Crop*, *Livestock*, *Shopkeeping*, etc.).

The results show a significant contrast in the community's reliance on these sectors. *Marine-related* activities are the leading choice for primary livelihoods (487 households vs 449 for non-marine). This is driven largely by *Fishing* and *Seaweed Farming*. While more households choose a marine activity as their first rank, non-marine activities are far more prevalent as secondary and tertiary livelihoods. For instance, in the 2nd Rank, non-marine activities (388 households) nearly double the marine activities

Table 1.2: Distribution of Livelihood Activities

Livelihood	1st livelihood	2nd livelihood	3rd livelihood	4th livelihood
Other Crop/Fruit/Vegetable Farming	347	221	62	40
Fishing	262	57	15	12
Other (Specify)	118	95	55	49
Seaweed Farming	115	63	24	8
Shopkeeping / Small-Scale Trading (Non-Fish)	61	39	19	11
Poultry Farming	50	68	50	33
Fish Trading	31	19	11	11
Other Food Product Preparation/Selling	29	29	15	2
Livestock Keeping (Goats, Cattle)	17	60	42	19
Fish Frying	8	9	5	4
Gleaning	4	10	3	3
Spice Farming	4	7	5	2
Fish Farming	3	5	3	3
Beekeeping	2	3	4	1
Fish Processing (e.g., Drying, Salting)	1	0	2	0
Crab Fattening	1	0	1	0
Sponge Farming	1	3	1	1
Sea Cucumber Farming	0	4	2	2
Salt Making	0	2	2	3
Not Specified (NaN)	0	0	0	0

(211). The data suggest that marine livelihoods are often treated as a "main" occupation. In contrast, non-marine livelihoods (such as poultry or livestock) appear to be the preferred means of economic diversification, providing steady supplemental income to the primary household. A significant number of households (118 primary) utilize "Other" livelihoods, indicating a diverse range of informal or niche economic activities not explicitly captured in the standard categories.

Table 1.3: Comparison of Marine vs. Non-Marine Livelihoods by Ranking

Category	1 (Primary)	2	3	4
Marine Related	487	211	88	58
Non-Marine Related	449	388	178	97
Other / Unspecified	118	95	55	49

Livelihood opportunities mentioned by respondents are most likely to be adopted

When evaluating the community's aspirations, we observe a clear split between those seeking to deepen their involvement in the marine sector and those seeking to diversify into land-based activities. The most desired livelihood for the future is *Other Crop/Fruit/Vegetable Farming* (347 households), which is a non-marine activity. This suggests a strong interest in agriculture as a pathway for economic growth and stability. *Fishing* remains the second most desired livelihood (262 households), indicating that many still see value in deepening their engagement with marine resources. The high interest in *Other (Specify)* (118 households) underscores the community's desire for diverse, potentially innovative livelihood options that may not be currently categorized.

The interest in marine-related activities remains the most frequent top-priority aspiration, with 487 respondents selecting a marine activity as their first choice for a new livelihood. This suggests that for many, the blue economy remains the most viable path to primary income growth. However, interest in Non-Marine Related activities dominates the secondary and tertiary ranks. While only 449 respondents chose a non-marine activity as their first potential choice, 388 chose one as their second, and 178 as their third—significantly, outperforming marine interests in these lower ranks. This pattern indicates that while community members may prioritize marine activities as their primary source of income, they view land-based options such as Poultry Farming and Livestock Keeping as the primary vehicles for household diversification and risk mitigation. Farming remains a universal interest, serving as both a primary aspiration and a widely desired secondary backup. The "Other" category remains significant across all ranks, underscoring the community's desire for a wide range of livelihood opportunities beyond traditional classifications.

Perception on the Status of Ecosystems and Resources

In Figure 1.2, we show the perceived reduction in catch levels. The fact that 342 respondents (approximately 87%) reported a difference in catch levels suggests that the decline is not an isolated observation but a widespread trend across the region. In small-scale fishing communities such as those in Pemba, such a high level of consensus often correlates with a genuine ecological tipping point or a significant increase in resource competition.

Table 1.4: Potential Livelihood Activities Respondents Wish to Pursue

Livelihood Option	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3
Other Crop/Fruit/Vegetable Farming	347	221	62
Fishing	262	57	15
Other (Specify)	118	95	55
Seaweed Farming	115	63	24
Shopkeeping / Small-Scale Trading (Non-Fish)	61	39	19
Poultry Farming	50	68	50
Fish Trading	31	19	11
Other Food Product Preparation/Selling	29	29	15
Livestock Keeping (Goats, Cattle)	17	60	42
Fish Frying	8	9	5
Gleaning	4	10	3
Spice Farming	4	7	5
Fish Farming	3	5	3
Beekeeping	2	3	4
Fish Processing (e.g., Drying, Salting)	1	0	2
Crab Fattening	1	0	1
Sponge Farming	1	3	1
Sea Cucumber Farming	0	4	2
Salt Making	0	2	2
Not Specified (NaN)	0	0	0

Figure 1.2: Perception of reduction in catch levels in Pemba East.

Table 1.5: Summary of Potential Livelihood Interests (Marine vs. Non-Marine)

Category	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3
Marine Related	487	211	88
Non-Marine Related	449	388	178
Other / Unspecified	118	95	55

When identifying the "why" behind these changes, the community points to two dominant factors:

- **Overfishing:** With 132 responses, this is the most frequently cited reason for declining catch levels. It reflects a local perception that increased fishing pressure, whether from more fishers, more efficient gear, or unsustainable practices, is depleting fish stocks faster than they can replenish.
- **Climate Change:** With 52 responses, this is the second most cited reason. It indicates that a significant portion of the community now links changes in catch levels to broader environmental shifts, such as rising sea temperatures, altered monsoon patterns, and impacts on coral reef health, all of which are known to affect fish populations in the Western Indian Ocean.

Figure 1.3: Perception of coral reef degradation in Pemba East.

In Figure 1.3, we show the perceived degradation of coral reefs. The survey results from Pemba indicate that while a majority of respondents (54%) report coral reef degradation, a large portion (35%) does not, and about 10% are unsure. This mixed perception is particularly interesting in light of recent scientific data from the Western Indian Ocean (WIO) [McClanahan et al., 2021, McClanahan, 2022]. While 213 people observed the damage, the 139 "No" responses may reflect the high resilience of certain local reef patches or limited underwater visibility among non-divers.

Table 1.6: Community Support for Conservation and MPA Management

Response	Benefits of Conservation	MPA as Management Tool
Yes	337	352
No	44	26
I don't know	10	13
Total Support %	86.2%	90.0%

Perception Towards Conservation and Management Needs

The survey also asked about perceptions of conservation and support for the creation of the new MCA (Table 1.6). The survey shows an overwhelmingly positive attitude towards conservation and formal management structures. With over 85% of respondents recognizing the benefits of habitat protection and even more (over 90%) believing in the efficacy of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), there is a clear "social license" for conservation initiatives in Pemba.

The finding that 352 respondents believe an MPA can help manage the marine environment is critical. It suggests that the community does not view MPAs as "restrictive zones" imposed from the outside, but rather as necessary tools for ensuring long-term resource availability.

People recognize that healthy habitats (mangroves, seagrass, and coral) produce tangible benefits—likely linked to the "spillover effect," in which protected areas replenish surrounding fishing grounds. Even some individuals who might be skeptical about general "conservation" still see the practical value of an MPA as a management framework. This suggests the community prioritizes order and regulation to address the overfishing concerns identified in your previous data.

The "No" and "I don't know" responses are notably low (roughly 6-11%). In many coastal regions, MPAs face stiff resistance due to the loss of fishing grounds. These results indicate that the current sentiment in Pemba is heavily skewed toward a desire for intervention, perhaps because the perceived "cost" of declining catches (which 91% of your respondents noticed) now outweighs the "cost" of fishing restrictions.

Respondents also expressed a strong desire for increased enforcement and management measures to protect marine resources (Table 1.7). The overwhelming support for increased patrols (doria) at 63.5% indicates that many community members see enforcement as a critical gap in current management efforts. This suggests that while there is strong support for conservation, there is also a recognition that without effective enforcement, the benefits of protected areas may not be realized. This signifies a widespread perception that current management is ineffective due to poor compliance and a lack of enforcement against illegal or unsustainable resource use. Spatial and Technical Control respondents also support the creation of closed areas (51.6%), and a significant number also desire stronger gear restrictions (45.3%). This demonstrates community willingness to accept and support measures that physically protect marine resources and limit destructive fishing practices.

Basic Necessity Survey Results

The overall Basic Necessity Score for each item or service was calculated at the household level (Table 1.8). The households were divided into two categories: those engaged in fishing-related activities

Table 1.7: Preferred management measure from the socioeconomic survey respondents

Desired Management Measure	Count Requested	% of Total Respondents
Doria (Patrols)	682	63.50%
Permanent and temporary closure	554	51.60%
Gear restrictions	486	45.30%
Other	273	25.40%

and those in non-fishing-related activities. The overall BNS score for East Pemba is 65% for all livelihoods, 66% for fishing-related households and 62% for non-fishing-related. Pemba was the only seascape surveyed in Tanzania, where fishers have a higher well-being than the rest of the community. From the BNS in Pemba, key findings reveal significant gaps in access to livelihood opportunities, food, electricity, and education.

Each service or item with a value of more than 50% is considered a necessity, and therefore, this item or service is deemed a necessity to sustain life. During the surveys, we found that most villages consider all items and services on our list to be very important for sustaining their lives. Interestingly, items such as Land Owned, Water Supply for Village, Primary School, Public Transport, Government Health Facility, Electricity, Generator, Phone Network 3 Meals per Day, Cooking Pot, Charcoal Stove, Cement Block Walls, Iron Sheet or Tiled Roof, Cement Floor, Flush Toilet (Private), Foam Mattress, Plate/Dish (Any Kind), Plastic Water Storage Container (20L+), Plastic Bucket (10L) and mobile Phone were scored as 90% or higher, meaning that they are highly needed items/services, in Pemba East North & South.

Table 1.8: BNS survey scores per item, separated by north and southeast Pemba

Items	Pemba Northeast		Pemba Southeast	
	Necessity	Have	Necessity	Have
3 Meals per Day	97%	33%	98%	35%
Cooking Pot	99%	99%	99%	99%
Charcoal Stove	90%	43%	90%	32%
Cement Block Walls in House	90%	40%	92%	49%
Iron Sheet or Tiled Roof	93%	65%	95%	82%
Cement Floor	93%	64%	94%	65%
Flush Toilet (Private)	95%	47%	95%	43%
Foam Mattress (Any Size)	95%	73%	98%	85%
Plate/Dish (Any Kind)	100%	98%	100%	99%
Wooden Chair or Stool	89%	41%	82%	36%
New Clothes 2 Times per Year	91%	27%	92%	22%
Plastic Water Storage Container	97%	72%	95%	48%

For Pemba East North, only four of these items, Cooking Pot, Plate/Dish (Any Kind), Plastic

Bucket (10L), and Access to Phone Network, were possessed by 90% of respondents. In Pemba East South, the list is the same, plus the access for Primary schools. Biggest discrepancies, greater than 50% difference, between percentage perceived need of item and percentage that possessed the item were; 3 Meals per Day, Cement Block Walls in House, New Clothes 2 Times per Year, Umbrella, Electric Radio, TV With Satellite, Cabinet/Cupboard, Electric Iron, Refrigerator (Privately Owned), Computer (Privately Owned), Owned fishing equipment (nets, traps, hook/line, etc.) and Electricity in Home for Pemba East North. In Pemba East South, the list is the same except for the addition of a charcoal stove and Flush Toilets.

Conclusions

The survey findings highlight the intersection between community well-being and the viability of marine conservation interventions. Economic stability in Pemba East is fundamentally anchored in the reliance on agriculture and marine related livelihoods. While farming provides the most widespread primary livelihood, marine livelihoods dominate when combining fishing, fish processing and trading and seaweed farming. In the communities, this dependency is managed through risk mitigation strategies, with households maintaining non-marine activities like poultry and livestock keeping as secondary buffers. However, a significant gap remains between perceived needs and actual possession of basic necessities—specifically regarding electricity, consistent nutrition, and healthcare—which serves as a critical metric for the long-term success of any project-based intervention with the level of overall wellbeing that remains low.

There is an overwhelming community consensus regarding the decline of natural resources, with approximately 87% of respondents noting a reduction in fish catches. This awareness has translated into a strong mandate for marine conservation with over 90% of residents that support initiatives in support of marine conservation like the creation of the new Marine Protected Areas, viewing them as essential tools for resource replenishment rather than external restrictions. Notably, there is a clear demand for improvements in enforcement, indicating that the community perceives a lack of compliance as the primary threat to their livelihoods.

Ultimately, these findings serve as a reminder that conservation initiatives cannot succeed in isolation from livelihood needs. By prioritizing wellbeing development, alongside marine conservation, stakeholders can work toward a management model where ecological protection and improved living standards are mutually reinforcing.

1.2 Climate-Change Risk Assessment

1.2.1 Introduction and Methodology

A village-level climate risk in Pemba North and Pemba South was calculated using data from the two surveys: the socio-economic survey (SES) and the basic necessities survey (BNS), which were conducted to characterize climate risk in terms of hazard, vulnerability, and exposure. As explained in detail in the previous section, the BNS gathered information on household-level well-being by asking whether households had access to a list of community-determined material goods and services. This information was used to calculate the BNS score for each household, which represents the percentage of basic necessities available to it. The BNS score is used as a proxy for well-being and is inversely related to exposure in the climate risk calculation. The SES covered a broad range of topics, including observations of occurrences of climate change threats and perceptions of climate change impacts on their livelihoods, which were used to represent hazard and vulnerability, respectively, in the climate risk calculation. This framework aligns with the standard Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) risk model, which quantifies risk as a function of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability [Kc et al., 2021]. This interaction implies that risk is not solely determined by biophysical impacts but is also shaped by socio-economic and cultural traits that modify a system's resistance and resilience. Specifically, vulnerability is defined as the system's sensitivity and adaptive capacity to cope with the adverse effects of climate stressors. This study then adopts these concepts by integrating household-level socio-economic indicators with observed environmental stressors to generate a composite risk index for specific climate threats. The specific climate threats assessed in this framework include coastal erosion, flooding, changes in rainfall and heat, changes in wind, and changes in water temperature.

Hazard, vulnerability, and exposure were calculated for each village and each climate threat, but statistical analysis revealed that differences in the BNS score among villages were not significant. Accordingly, the BNS score was calculated for the region and used to represent exposure across all villages in the region (Table 1.9).

The final village climate risk score was computed using the formula 1.1, which multiplies hazard, exposure, and vulnerability and averages across the five climate threats. The villages with the highest climate risk scores were identified as priority areas for intervention and conservation efforts. Exposure is calculated as $(1 - BNS)$ to reflect the inverse relationship between well-being and exposure to climate risks.

$$CRS_V = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{T=1}^5 P_{Village,Threat} \times (1 - BNS_{Region}) \times V_{Village,Threat} \quad (1.1)$$

In the equation above, CRS_V represents the Climate Risk Score for a given village, and the summation is taken over the five assessed climate threats. Each term in the summation is a product of the perceived hazard ($P_{Village,Threat}$), the inverse of the Basic Necessities Score ($1 - BNS_{Region}$) representing exposure, and the vulnerability ($V_{Village,Threat}$) of the village to that specific threat. The resulting CRS_V provides a composite measure of the overall climate risk faced by each village, enabling identification of the most vulnerable to climate change impacts and prioritizing them for targeted interventions.

Table 1.9: Climate Risk Assessment Variables and Survey Questions

Assessment Variable	Survey	Scale	Survey Questions
Hazard	Socio-Economic Survey	Village	Have you observed any coastal erosion in your village?
			Do you experience any floods in the village with high tides and storms?
			Have you observed changes in rain and heat trends?
			Have you observed any changes in the strength of winds?
			Have you observed any changes in water temperature?
Vulnerability	Socio-Economic Survey	Village	Which of the above events affects your livelihoods the most?
Exposure	Basic Necessities Survey	Region	Do you have [select from list of community-defined material goods and services]?
			Is it necessary?

1.2.2 Results

Hazards and Vulnerability by Climate Threat

Hazard, measured as the frequency of climate threats reported by respondents, is shown in Figure 1.4. Changes in heat and rainfall, wind, and water temperature were reported by 81%, 74%, and 78% of household respondents, respectively (Figure 1.4). This is consistent with the scientific literature on climate change impacts in the Western Indian Ocean, which has documented significant increases in sea surface temperatures, changes in rainfall patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events. Coastal erosion and flooding were reported by a smaller percentage of respondents (approximately 48% and 27%, respectively), which may reflect the localized nature of these hazards or lower awareness among respondents.

For Vulnerability, measured as the proportion of respondents who selected a threat as the one most affecting their livelihoods, heat, rainfall, and wind were the two most impactful climate threats (38% and 34% of respondents, respectively). This suggests that while many respondents are aware of multiple climate threats, they perceive changes in heat and rainfall as having the most direct and significant impact on their livelihoods. This is likely because changes in heat and rainfall can directly affect agricultural productivity, whereas changes in wind patterns and strength can affect fishing activities and marine-related livelihoods, such as fish processing and seaweed farming.

In Figure 1.5, we show the hazard observations by village. Spatial distribution of hazard observations across villages in Pemba North and Pemba South reveals that certain villages report higher frequencies of specific climate threats. For instance, villages located in the north reported more frequent floods than villages in the south, which were instead most commonly affected by changes in heat and rainfall.

Figure 1.4: On the left panel, a measure of hazard calculated as the percentage of respondents who selected a given Threat. On the right panel, a measure of Vulnerability calculated how often a threat was selected as the one most affecting the respondent's livelihood.

Regarding the vulnerability, the map reveals a distinct latitudinal gradient in the perception of climate threats across Pemba Island. In the northern and northeastern regions, such as around Msuka Mashariki and Kinowe, the distribution is heavily dominated by atmospheric threats, specifically winds and changes in rain. This suggests that northern livelihoods are particularly sensitive to shifts in monsoonal patterns and to unpredictable precipitation. As we move toward the central-eastern coast, heat becomes a more pronounced factor, while wind remains a primary concern for communities such as Kangagani.

A significant shift occurs in the southern half of the island (Figure 1.5), particularly from Vitongoji down to Mkwajuni. Here, the "wet" physical threats of coastal erosion, floods, and water temperature become much more prominent than in the north. The high reporting of water temperature in the southernmost clusters is especially critical, as it likely reflects the vulnerability of local seaweed farming and reef-based fisheries to thermal stress. Ultimately, the geography of vulnerability on Pemba shifts from a focus on weather and storm patterns in the north to one on sea-level rise and marine warming impacts in the south.

This spatial variation in hazard and vulnerability observations is crucial for understanding localized climate risks and tailoring interventions accordingly. The vulnerability map indicates that while many villages experience multiple climate threats, the perceived impact on livelihoods varies, with some villages identifying specific threats as more detrimental than others. This underscores the importance of accounting for both hazard frequency and perceived vulnerability when assessing climate risk at the village level.

The final score for each village is a composite of these two factors, weighted by the overall exposure of the region as determined by the BNS score, and is shown in Figure 1.6 and calculated in equation 1.1. Results for Climate Risk Score (CRS) are shown in Table 1.10. The CRS provides a quantitative measure of the overall climate risk faced by each village, enabling the identification of the most vulnerable to climate change impacts and prioritizing them for targeted interventions. Results show that the villages with the highest climate risk scores are located in the northern and southern parts of Pemba Island, with a cluster of high-risk villages in the northeast and another cluster in the southeast.

Figure 1.5: On the left panel, a measure of hazard calculated as the percentage of respondents who selected a given Threat. In the right panel, a measure of Vulnerability was calculated as the frequency with which a threat was selected as the one most affecting the respondent’s livelihood.

This spatial pattern suggests that certain areas of Pemba may be more vulnerable to climate change impacts than others, likely due to a combination of factors such as proximity to the coast, geography, slope and elevation, exposure to the wind, but also reliance on climate-sensitive livelihoods, and existing levels of well-being as indicated by the BNS scores. The ten villages in Pemba North and Pemba South with the highest climate risk scores are Chamboni, Kojani, Shanake, Kiungoni, Msuka Mashariki, Msuka Magharibi, Tumbé Magharibi, Tumbé Mashariki, Mjini Wingwi, and Kinowe. Two additional villages initially ranked in the top ten when analyzed using village-level BNS scores: Kiuyu Mbuyuni and Sizini. These two villages may also warrant further investigation and intervention. See Table 1.10 for all climate risk scores for the Pemba North and Pemba South Regions.

An example of a village with a high climate risk score from this assessment is Kojani. Every community member surveyed in Kojani reported observing changes in heat and rainfall trends, wind strength, and water temperature. A majority also reported observing coastal erosion (86%) and flooding (71%). For each of these threats, at least a small percentage (>5%) of community members reported that it impacts their livelihoods, with most (57%) reporting that changes in heat and rainfall impact their livelihoods. The resulting climate risk score for Kojani was above average because every threat had at least a low-to-medium impact on the community’s livelihood, and almost all community members observed all threats. Kojani is located in the Pemba North region and has a BNS score of 0.52, yielding a vulnerability score of 0.48. This does not significantly affect the final risk score, as it is only slightly between the other two regions. An example of a village with a low climate risk score from this assessment is Mpambani. Less than 50% of community members reported observing climate threats, and

of those, only two were reported to impact their livelihoods (winds and changes in heat and rainfall, both of which had low observation rates). Mpambani is also within the Pemba North region and has a BNS score of 0.52, translating into a vulnerability score of 0.48. This does not significantly affect the final risk score, as it is only slightly between the other two regions.

Figure 1.6: Climate Risk Score for Pemba and Tanga, where the same analysis was conducted.

1.2.3 Discussion

The Climate Risk Assessment (CRA) conducted in Pemba North and Pemba South provides valuable insights into the spatial distribution of climate risks across villages in these regions. The analysis revealed that certain villages, particularly those located in the northern and southern parts of Pemba Island, are more vulnerable to climate change impacts than others. This vulnerability is likely influenced by a combination of factors, including proximity to the coast, reliance on climate-sensitive livelihoods such as fishing and agriculture, and existing well-being levels, as indicated by the Basic Necessities Score (BNS). Identifying high-risk villages enables targeted interventions and conservation efforts to mitigate the impacts of climate change on vulnerable communities. It is crucial for stakeholders, including local governments, NGOs, and community leaders, to prioritize these high-risk areas for climate adaptation strategies, such as improving infrastructure, diversifying livelihoods, and enhancing community awareness and preparedness for climate-related hazards. Additionally, ongoing monitoring and reassessment of climate risks will be essential to ensure that interventions remain effective and responsive to changing conditions.

Table 1.10: Climate Risk Score for each sampled village. Scores are also disaggregated for fishers and non-fishers.

Village	Final CRS	CRS Fisher	CRS Non-Fisher	Ward	District
Chamboni	0.094	0.19	0.19	Micheweni	Micheweni
Kojani	0.092	0.19	0.19	Kojani	Wete
Shanake	0.090	0.19	0.19	Kiuyu Mbuyuni	Micheweni
Kiungoni	0.086	0.19	0.19	Kiungoni	Wete
Msuka Mashariki*	0.080	0.18	0.18	Msuka Mashariki	Micheweni
Msuka Magharibi*	0.080	0.18	0.18	Msuka Magharibi	Micheweni
Tumbe Magharibi	0.080	0.18	0.18	Tumbe Magharibi	Micheweni
Tumbe Mashariki	0.079	0.18	0.18	Tumbe Mashariki	Micheweni
Mjini Wingwi	0.077	0.18	0.18	Mjini Wingwi	Micheweni
Kinowe	0.077	0.18	0.18	Kinowe	Micheweni
Shumba Mjini	0.077	0.18	0.18	Shumba Mjini	Micheweni
Kibokoni	0.076	0.18	0.17	Kibokoni	Chake Chake
Sizini**	0.076	0.18	0.18	Sizini	Micheweni
Michungwani	0.076	0.18	0.17	Michungwani Shehia	Chake Chake
Kangagani	0.075	0.18	0.17	Kangagani	Wete
Kiuyu Mbuyuni**	0.073	0.17	0.17	Kiuyu Mbuyuni	Micheweni
Wingwi Mapofu	0.072	0.17	0.17	Wingwi Mapofu	Micheweni
Chambani	0.071	0.17	0.17	Chambani	Mkoani
Mwambe	0.070	0.17	0.17	Mwambe	Mkoani
Chole	0.070	0.17	0.17	Kengenja	Mkoani
Wingwi Njunguni	0.070	0.17	0.17	Wingwi Njuguni	Micheweni
Majenzi	0.068	0.17	0.17	Majenzi Ward	Micheweni
Kengeja	0.065	0.17	0.16	Kengenja	Mkoani
Mtemani	0.065	0.17	0.16	Uzi Shehia	Micheweni
Maziwa Ng'ombe	0.063	0.16	0.16	Maziwa	Micheweni
Mvumoni	0.059	0.16	0.16	Mvumoni Shehia	Chake Chake
Mtangani	0.058	0.16	0.16	Mtangani	Mkoani
Kiwani	0.057	0.16	0.15	Kiwani	Mkoani
Dodo	0.050	0.15	0.15	Dodo	Mkoani
Micheweni	0.047	0.15	0.15	Micheweni	Micheweni
Mchakwe	0.045	0.14	0.14	Muambe	Mkoani
Mpambani	0.035	0.14	0.13	Mpambani	Wete

Chapter 2

Ecological Surveys

2.1 Benthic Ecological Surveys (BES)

2.1.1 Introduction

To provide baseline data for the development and establishment of marine conservation areas, the Benthic Ecological Survey was conducted at Pemba East North and South, with the goal of mapping all shallow marine habitats around the island. The survey was conducted as part of a broader national effort, which resulted in an extensive dataset of coastal marine habitats. The survey aims to improve satellite-based benthic substrate datasets, which are often inaccurate in tropical coastal waters due to water turbidity and floating vegetation. The survey also aims to provide a more detailed characterization of benthic habitats, which is crucial for understanding the distribution of marine biodiversity and the potential impacts of human activities on these ecosystems. The data collected from the Benthic Ecological Survey will inform the design and management of marine conservation areas and support ongoing monitoring and research efforts in the region. The survey was not designed to replace more accurate but more costly diver-based surveys, but rather to provide a cost-effective and scalable method for mapping benthic habitats across large areas of coastal waters.

The method we present aims to bridge a gap in data-collection tools for benthic substrates (Figure 2.1). Common coral reef sampling protocols are appropriate for data collection at either small or large scales, but are typically inadequate for sampling benthic ecosystems at the scale of interest for community and local fishery management. Point and Line Intercept Transects and methods, and typical photoquadrat protocols, produce accurate and precise data but are limited to small scales ($\mathcal{O}(0.1 - 1) km^2$) due to the time and costs involved in diving on site. These methods also require high capacity and skills, which are not always available on the ground in remote areas and developing countries. Manta tows, a visual monitoring protocol, extends the survey scale by about one order of magnitude, enabling sampling of areas up to a few kilometers. This method compromises accuracy and precision but is faster and more cost-effective than PIT and LIT, albeit still requiring significant on-the-ground skills and capacity. On the opposite side of the spectrum, satellites are used to map the global distribution of coral reefs, but while the data is typically with high spatial resolution, its accuracy is limited, making it suitable only for large-scale assessments ($\mathcal{O}(100 - 1000) km^2$). While satellite data may seem adequate for local fishery management applications, given the availability of

data at relatively fine scales, it is important to note that the data provided may not be reliable and should be treated carefully [Mumby et al., 1997, Kennedy et al., 2021b].

Figure 2.1: Comparison of the sampling of common benthic assessment methods. Currently, there are no methods to effectively sample the scales between 10 and 100 km^2 .

Given the limitations with the existing monitoring approaches, WCS developed a methodology to fill the gap of scales between $O(10) km^2$ and $O(100) km^2$, trying to strike a balance between accuracy and precision that is appropriate for the application related to coastal fishery management and spatial planning. The existing methodology was then improved and applied to a large-scale, real-world application to map benthic substrate ecosystems along the entire Tanzanian coastline. The results for Pemba East, North, and South are shown below. In the first part of the report, we outline the methodology and its application in the field, focusing on the sampling design, the at-sea operations, and the data post-processing. Summary statistics are presented in the results, with a focus on the spatial distribution of the main benthic classes, including their abundance statistics, and on comparisons with the most commonly used satellite-derived coral reef products.

2.1.2 Methodology

The method was developed by WCS Tanzania in 2022 to map the waters around Misali Island in Pemba. The methodology was later improved and adapted for use in the waters around Pemba East, North, and South. The method uses underwater cameras to capture images of the benthic substrate, which are then analyzed to classify the habitat types present in the area. The camera was then lowered to a pre-selected georeferenced location, where images of the benthos were acquired and subsequently evaluated. In essence, it is a photo-quadrant technique that can be used with a small team and a small boat without the need for divers in the water.

Using materials purchased in Zanzibar, local welders constructed the frame, which measured roughly 1.5 m in length and 1 m in width (Figure 2.2). The GoPro camera with underwater housing was mounted on a metal bar at the top of the frame. To reduce distortion, the camera was configured with

Figure 2.2: Metal tripod mounted with a camera that was used to capture benthic images.

a "linear" lens. The image's maximum resolution was 4K. To conserve battery life, all superfluous camera features—such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, GPS, and the front screen—were disabled. The structure was made to be both stable and lightweight. To ensure stability during descent in the water, weights are placed on the frame's feet. The frame's base is sufficiently wide that it is not visible in the images. The operators lowered the frame from the side of a small fiberglass boat. The GoPro and an underwater case together enabled reaching a depth of 50 meters. A uniform grid with a 1-kilometer spacing was used in the survey design. Bathymetric stations with depths less than 65 meters were selected. The bathymetric layer (GEBCO 2023) was used to make the grid, which has a margin of error of several meters. An echo-sounder can be used to measure a station's real depth on the spot; if it is deeper than 50 meters, the operator can skip it.

The entire Pemba East, North, and South coastline for all depths shallower than 50 m was covered by the survey. In total, 863 stations were identified in the entire sample scheme, with 413 stations that were below the 50 m mark and were surveyed, resulting in over 1,239 photo quadrats being gathered by taking three replicas' photos of each station, a few meters apart (Figure 2.3).

Operations at Sea

When operating at sea, a small vessel uses a rope to lower the frame containing the underwater camera to predetermined depths. An echo-sounder was used to measure the station's depth before lowering the frame; if it was less than 50 meters, the camera was turned on and lowered to the ocean floor. The team navigated to a new station if the depth exceeded 50 m. At each new location, the camera was powered on and configured to capture an image every 2 s. To match the photos to the station number during image processing, a whiteboard with the site name and replica code (a, b, or c) was photographed. To allow the camera time to focus and adjust sensitivity in low light, the frame was left on the ocean floor for approximately 10 seconds. In the meantime, the boat pilot kept the vessel in place to prevent the frame from dragging. Afterward, the tripod was retrieved to construct a second replica. Three samples were taken at each site, and the boat was free to move between replicates. As a result, the replicates for each site were grouped together. Each replicate records the GPS location

Figure 2.3: Sampling design for the Benthic Ecological Survey. On the left panel, the grid of sampling stations along the Pemba East North and South coastline. In the right panel, a photo of the GoPro camera mounted on a metal tripod is used to capture images of the benthos.

from a portable GPS.

The operators record the GPS waypoint number, depth, time, and station number at each station. The team would document the survey date, survey area, and team members for each trip. Figure 3 displays an example of the metadata sheet. In addition to the captain, each team must include at least three members. One person handles the frame, another enters the data, and a third navigates the station. This method enables each team to sample approximately 50 stations per day. To provide space for the exercise the following day, the camera's photos were transferred to a computer on the day of each mission. Photographs are cleaned and sorted in the office at the conclusion of each mission leg, removing any undesirable images. Most images are not of the benthic substrate because the camera is elevated and lowered from the bottom every 2 s. The best image from each station was selected, replicated, renamed according to the site name, and backed up prior to processing.

Image Classification

CoralNet, an online, open-source database that facilitates the labeling and archiving of picture quadrats, is then used to upload and process the photographs. Excel was used to digitize the metadata

and connect it to the portable device's GPS coordinates. A group of specialists educated by the WCS coral reef team labels the substrates in CoralNet. By classifying the image into 21 substrate groups, the percentage of substrate cover was calculated (Table 2.1). On a random, organized grid, CoralNet was set up to sample 25 points per image. To remove the most distorted region of the image, 10% of the frame was clipped on each side. The remaining frame is divided into 25 grids of the same size. One random point is sampled from each grid. The user would determine the substrate for each location. After a few photos have been manually tagged, CoralNet employs a machine learning model to begin generating label suggestions with progressively higher confidence. For simple substrates such as sand and seagrass, this method performs reasonably well, but it requires extensive training for more complex substrates. A non-expert can quickly and easily recognize the label set. The goal of this application was to quickly and scalably quantify important functional groups, even though the image quality would enable the classification of corals to the family and possibly genus level. Nevertheless, the collected dataset can be reviewed in future research to extract more specific data. Depending on the complexity of the substrates, labeling may take many days. While coral reef sections would take a long time to label, most samples were sand or seagrass, making labeling reasonably quick. An estimated 10% of the photos were analyzed for 90% of the time.

Labels are downloaded from the website and linked to the metadata file, including GPS data, once all images have been examined. The percentages of each label are computed for every station. The percentage coverage values for each label at each station are then computed by averaging the GPS positions and benthic coverage values across replicates. This dataset is one of the primary outputs of the benthic ecological survey. The WCS coral reef monitoring team carried out the labeling. It was crucial to evaluate the labeling error rate using a post-validation procedure, despite all employees having received prior training and the labeling covering only simple categories. With a combined 50 years of coral reef monitoring experience, the two most seasoned coral reef professionals at WCS oversaw the validation. A sample of 150 photos—roughly 25 each seascape—was used for the validation. Images from the pool of photos with a hard coral percentage greater than zero were perhaps the most difficult to identify. The validation procedure revealed error rates of 5%, 10%, and 15% for the seagrass, sand, and hard coral categories, respectively. The error rate for the hard coral category was higher than that of the other categories because it was more difficult to identify and classify, and because fewer photos of hard coral were available, which made it more difficult to train the machine learning model. The error rates for the seagrass and sand categories were lower because they were easier to identify and classify, and because there were more photos with these substrates, which made it easier to train the machine learning model. Overall, the validation procedure showed that the labeling was reasonably accurate, but that there is room for improvement, particularly in the classification of hard coral. Error rates across categories should be considered when interpreting the results of the benthic ecological survey, and efforts should be made to improve labeling accuracy in future surveys, particularly for the hard coral category.

2.1.3 Results

Spatial distribution and abundance of main benthic substrates

Figure 2.4 displays data for four main variables extracted from the CoralNet data.

- *Reef*: This quantity is calculated as the sum of all live hard coral morphological labels, plus the

Table 2.1: CoralNet Benthic Categories and Functional Groups

CoralNet Code	Name of Category	Functional Group
HC	Generic hard coral	coral reef associated
HC Branching	Hard coral branching	coral reef associated
HC Encrusting	Hard coral encrusting	coral reef associated
HC Massive	Hard coral massive	coral reef associated
Porites branching	Hard coral Porites	coral reef associated
SC	Soft corals	coral reef associated
SP	Sponges	coral reef associated
CCA Crustose	Coralline algae	coral reef associated
Halimeda	Halimeda algae	algae
AL_Freshy	Algae (Fleshy)	algae
Turf	Turf alga	algae
D Coral	Dead coral	coral reef disturbance
Rubble	Rubble	coral reef disturbance
Sand	Sand	other habitats
Shell hash	Shell hash/Gravel	other habitats
Rock	Bare rock	other habitats
Seagrass	Seagrass	other habitats
EURR	Echinoderms: sea urchins	indicator species
HOL	Holothuroidea: sea cucumber	indicator species
No data	No data	other
OTH	Others	other

soft corals and the sponges. It is meant to represent a coral reef in a broader sense than strictly hard live corals.

- *Coral*: The sum of all live hard coral morphological labels. This is what is typically measured and reported as hard coral cover.
- *Seagrass*: It's an important ecological habitat for biodiversity and fisheries.
- *Rubble*: Fragments or corals. It is presented to show areas that have undergone recent damage, either due to the use of destructive gears or natural events.

Figure 2.4: Results of the BES survey in northern Pemba are shown, with larger circles indicating higher percentage coverage. The proposed boundaries are shown in purple. Top left – hard coral cover. Top right – seagrass cover. Bottom middle – rubble cover.

In the northern part of Pemba East, Coral and Reef variables exhibit nearly identical spatial patterns, primarily restricted to the outer shelf and the seaward edges of the reef crest. The highest concentrations are found in the northern offshore section and along the narrow eastern shelf, following the bathymetric contours where water energy is likely higher. A few patches with high coral cover (near 50%) can be found in the north east of the bay and off Kojani Island. Seagrass is the most dominant and widely distributed variable, particularly concentrated in shallow, sheltered inner-lagoon areas and coastal fringes. The highest densities (up to 100%) are found in the northern bay and along the western coastlines. Rubble is scattered across the northern lagoon and along the eastern coast. Interestingly, it often occurs in transition zones between high-density seagrass beds and outer coral-reef areas, likely representing areas of reef degradation or high-energy transport.

In the southern part of the domain (Figure 2.5), the benthic maps show a distinct spatial arrangement of habitats, characterized by a sharp division between the sheltered western inlets and the exposed eastern shelf. Coral and Reef, similar to the northern sector, are tightly coupled and follow the narrow bathymetric shelf along the eastern coastline. They are most prominent on the seaward edge of the reef, with notable high-density clusters appearing on the fringing reefs south of the main eastern peninsula. Seagrass is almost exclusively concentrated within the complex network of bays and lagoons on the western side of the island, particularly near Mkoani and the areas south of Chake Chake. Large, high-density patches (80–100%) are prevalent in these protected, shallow waters. Rubble distribution is relatively sparse in this southern section compared to the north. It appears in small, isolated patches along the eastern reef edge and occasionally at the mouths of the western inlets, likely indicating areas where wave energy breaks down reef structures or where tidal currents are strongest. Notably, the type of survey we conducted, with a spacing of 1 km, is not ideal for this type of fringing reef, where it's likely that the entire eastern part of the island has a narrow fringing reef with soft and hard corals, which was likely missed by the survey design.

Figure 2.5: Results of the BES survey in southern Pemba are shown, with larger circles indicating higher percentage coverage. The proposed boundaries are shown in purple. Top left – hard coral cover. Top right – seagrass cover. Bottom middle – rubble cover.

Table 2.2 shows summary statistics for hard live coral and seagrass over a total area of 413 km² shallowed to 50 m. The results highlight a significant disparity between the extent of seagrass and hard coral habitats within the region. Seagrass is the most prevalent high-value habitat, with 122 km² (approximately 29.7% of the survey area) containing at least 5% cover. Even at high densities (> 50%), seagrass retains a substantial footprint of 56 km² (13.6%). Hard coral habitats are comparatively rare. Only 7.8% (32 km²) of the surveyed area contains more than 5% hard coral cover. Areas of exceptional ecological value — defined by high-density cover — are very restricted for corals, totaling just 1 km² (0.24%) for areas with coral cover > 50% and 9 km² (2.1%) for areas with coral cover > 20%. In contrast, high-density seagrass meadows are much more common, covering 56 km² for areas with seagrass cover > 50% and 99 km² (24.14%) for areas with seagrass cover > 20%. This quantitative data supports the spatial observations from the maps: while seagrass forms large, continuous meadows in the sheltered western and northern lagoons, the hard coral communities are confined to much smaller, specialized niches along the outer reef slopes.

Table 2.2: Coverage in area and percentage of the coral reef and seagrass areas.

Substrate	Area (km ²)	% of Survey
All substrates	413	100%
Hard Coral > 5%	32	7.8%
Hard Coral > 20%	9	2.1%
Hard Coral > 50%	1	0.24%
Seagrass > 5%	122	29.7%
Seagrass > 20%	99	24.14%
Seagrass > 50%	56	13.6%

Statistics on benthic substrates

The quantitative analysis of benthic classes across the entire survey area provides a comprehensive view of the seafloor composition. Figure 2.6 shows a landscape dominated by soft sediments and fleshy algae, with key habitat-forming organisms like coral and seagrass occupying smaller, more specialized niches. Sand is the most prevalent benthic class, accounting for nearly half of the total area (46.7%). This aligns with the extensive lagoon systems observed in the spatial maps. Fleshy algae (AL_fleshy) represent a significant portion of the benthos at 15.8%. When combined with other organic classes like Halimeda (1.4%) and CCA (0.9%), it suggests a highly productive but non-reef-building environment in many sectors. Seagrass and Coral represent 8.6% and 4.5% of the total coverage, respectively. While these percentages seem low compared to sand, they represent the high-value ecological zones critical for biodiversity in Pemba. Rubble (5.9%) and Rock (4.9%) provide the necessary hard substrate for coral recruitment, though the presence of rubble can also indicate areas of past reef physical disturbance. Other categories, such as ShellHash (2.4%), Sponges (SP, 2.0%), and Soft Corals (SC, 3.5%), round out the diversity of the survey area.

This breakdown suggests that while Pemba's waters are characterized by vast sandy lagoons, the actual "engine" of the ecosystem—the coral and seagrass—is concentrated in less than 15% of the total

Figure 2.6: Distribution of benthic classes across the entire survey area. The pie chart shows the percentage of the total area covered by each substrate class, while the bar chart provides a more detailed breakdown of the relative abundance of each class.

surveyed area.

In Figure 2.7 we look instead for each photoquadrant at the frequency of images with various percentages of substrates. The frequency distribution of substrates across the photoquadrats provides a clear picture of the habitat heterogeneity in the survey area. While the pie chart showed the total "budget" of the benthos, these frequency distributions (histograms of cover) reveal how those materials are actually organized on the seafloor.

- **Sand (Bimodal/Skewed Toward 100%)**: The observation that most quadrats contained 100% sand confirms that the lagoonal system consists of vast, homogenous sandy plains. This suggests that where sand is present, it tends to exclude other substrates entirely.
- **Hard Coral, Rubble, Rock, and Fleshy Algae (Inverse/Right-Skewed)**: The "opposite" distribution for these variables—where most areas have almost no presence—indicates that these substrates are highly localized.
 - Hard Coral: The fact that most quadrats have < 40% cover with only a few "hotspots" suggests that Pemba's reefs are not continuous carpets of coral but rather discrete patches or narrow bands along the shelf edge, associated with underwater features topological or hydrological.
 - Rubble and Rock: These follow a similar pattern, appearing as occasional features rather than dominant regional covers.
- **Seagrass (Uniform/Broad Distribution)**: Unlike the others, seagrass is somewhat more uniform across various percentages. This implies a high degree of "mixed" habitat, in which

Figure 2.7: Histograms of the distribution of points per quadrant.

seagrass may transition from sparse patches to dense meadows, rather than being an "all-or-nothing" substrate like sand.

This frequency data indicate that while Hard Coral > 50% cover is rare (0.24% of the area), the few photoquadrats that exhibit it represent critical "source" reefs that likely require the highest level of protection within a Marine Protected Area (MPA) framework.

Figure 2.8: 2D histograms showing the dependence of Hard Coral and Seagrass on depth.

The spatial distribution of substrates is likely depth-dependent, with different substrates occupying distinct ecological niches. We can examine this by computing 2D histograms for the various benthic substrates. In Figure 2.8 we show the dependence of the Hard Coral and Seagrass with depth. The 2D histograms reveal a clear bathymetric zonation of benthic substrates, confirming that depth is a primary driver of habitat distribution in the Pemba survey area. This depth-dependence creates a distinct transition from shallow-water specialists to those adapted to the shelf edge.

- *Hard Coral and Reef Shelf-Edge Specialization:* Hard coral and reef structures are primarily concentrated at the transition zone between 10 m and 30 m. The 2D histograms likely show a "band" of presence along the steeper bathymetric gradients of the eastern shelf.
- *Seagrass Dominance in the Shallows:* In contrast to Hard Coral, Seagrass exhibits a strong preference for shallow waters, with the highest point density and cover percentages clustered between 0 m and 10 m depth. This aligns with its physiological requirement for high light availability for photosynthesis.
- *Sand and Rubble Transitions:* Sand remains the most bathymetrically versatile substrate, appearing across all depth bins, though it dominates the flat lagoonal depths. Rubble appears most frequently in the 5–15 m range, often acting as a physical transition between the inner seagrass beds and the outer reef crest.

Comparison with Satellite Layers

Lastly, we can compare our results with data from satellite-based coral distribution layers. A common approach to mapping the global distribution of coral reef areas is to train models on satellite imagery to identify features that resemble coral reefs. This methodology enables the production of high-detail maps over large areas. The downside of this approach is that the models must be calibrated using in-situ observations, which are sparse and typically available only in coral reef areas. Here, we compare the most commonly available products with our results to assess whether these models can be used instead of in-situ observations for coastal management.

The products we are considering in this comparison are the

- Allen Coral Atlas [Kennedy et al., 2021a], a model built by Paul Allen's Vulcan Inc. and managed by the Arizona State University Center for Global Discovery and Conservation Science. The Atlas uses a 4-band mosaic, including near infrared, to generate the classifications. In the following, we compare two variables from this model: *Coral/Algae* distribution (AA) and *Reef Extent* (AA_RE) variable. Reef Extent in this context is defined as the location of shallow coral reef features that can generally be seen from satellites. It typically excludes areas of very deep and very turbid water.
- UNEP-WCMC [UNEP-WCMC et al., 2021], Global Distribution of Coral Reefs. This dataset was compiled from multiple sources by the UNEP World Conservation Monitoring Centre (UNEPWCMC) and the WorldFish Centre, in collaboration with WRI (World Resources Institute) and TNC (The Nature Conservancy). Data sources include the Millennium Coral Reef Mapping Project (IMaRS-USF and IRD 2005, IMaRS-USF 2005) and the World Atlas of Coral Reefs.

Figure 2.9: Maps showing the location of the BES stations (black dots) the areas with live hard coral (blue dots), and the areas with coral cover according to the three satellite layers we are considering in this comparison.

The datasets are produced using similar methodologies, but the results can vary. Looking at distributional examples in our geographies, we see that the datasets cover somewhat different areas. Figure 2.9 shows the same area in Msuka Bay, north of Pemba, with the areas covered by the BES survey, the coral cover values found during the survey, and how these compare with the data on coral cover from the satellite layers overlaid. The maps show large differences among the satellite layers, between the satellite layers, and the BES results. In general, the satellite layers tend to overestimate the extent of coral reef areas, but several coral reef areas are completely missed by the satellite layers.

Comparing in-situ observations with satellite-derived products—such as the Allen Coral Atlas (ACA) or UNEP-WCMC layers—reveals a critical trade-off between spatial scale and ecological accuracy. While satellite models offer unprecedented coverage, the "inverse" distribution and patchy nature of high-value habitats in Pemba highlight specific limitations in remote sensing for local management. The in-situ data show that high-density coral (> 50%) is extremely restricted (0.24% of the area). Global satellite products often aggregate these small, high-value patches into larger pixels

(5 m to 30 m), leading to an overestimation of reef extent and an underestimation of live coral cover within those pixels. Satellite models typically struggle in waters deeper than 15-20 m or in turbid lagoonal areas. The 2D histograms confirm that Pemba's reefs are shelf-edge specialists (peaking at 15-25 m), meaning a significant portion of the most productive reef might be "invisible" or misclassified as sand/rubble in satellite layers. The broad, uniform distribution of seagrass in the survey is often better captured by satellites than the patchy "hotspots" of coral. However, the transition zones (rubble/rock) are frequently "noised out" in satellite models, which prefer clean classifications of "Coral" vs. "Sand."

2.1.4 Conclusions

The spatial distribution of benthic substrates in Pemba is strongly governed by bathymetric gradients, leading to distinct ecological zonation. Seagrass meadows are the primary shallow-water specialists, with their highest density and point frequency concentrated in the 0–12 m depth range. This distribution is likely limited by light attenuation, as these autotrophic communities require high levels of photosynthetically active radiation found in the upper photic zone. In contrast, hard corals and reef-associated structures occupy a much narrower, deeper niche, peaking along the shelf edge between 15 m and 25 m. This bathymetric separation suggests that while seagrass dominates the sheltered, shallow lagoons, the reef-building communities are restricted to the high-energy, clearer waters of the outer slopes.

The ubiquity of sand across all depth bins underscores the sedimentary nature of the Pemba coastline, although its highest occurrence is in the flat, low-energy interior basins. Rubble is most frequent in the transition zones between 10m and 15m, often marking the boundary between physical reef degradation and wave energy focusing. This niche partitioning underscores the vulnerability of high-integrity habitats: because "coral gardens" are confined to a narrow depth band, they are disproportionately exposed to localized threats, such as sedimentation from land-based runoff or temperature anomalies that affect specific layers of the water column.

Comparing these in-situ findings with satellite-based distribution layers reveals significant discrepancies that impact coastal management. Satellite models often perform spatial smoothing by aggregating fragmented coral patches and intervening rubble into a single "Reef" classification. While this is useful for broad regional assessments, it tends to overestimate the actual live coral cover. Furthermore, light attenuation in deeper waters often introduces a "shallow-water bias" in remote sensing products, potentially causing models to miss the deeper, high-integrity reef slopes identified in this survey at depths exceeding 18 m. Consequently, while seagrass meadows are generally well-captured due to their large and uniform footprints, the rare and patchy coral hotspots remain difficult to monitor without direct observation.

The extreme rarity of high-integrity habitats in Pemba mandates a highly targeted management strategy. Since "coral gardens" with > 50% cover represent less than 1% of the coastline and are confined to a narrow depth band (15-25 m), broad, non-spatial regulations may fail to protect these specific ecological engines. Instead, management should prioritize establishing small no-take zones around these high-density hotspots. This approach ensures the protection of critical larval sources while minimizing the socio-economic impact on local fishers by leaving the vast majority of the coastline accessible. Furthermore, the vertical zonation of these reefs suggests a need for depth-specific gear

regulations, such as prohibiting bottom-contact fishing and anchoring along the shelf edge to prevent physical damage to the deeper, high-relief structures. Finally, a holistic "lagoon-to-slope" model must be adopted to maintain connectivity between the shallow seagrass nurseries (0-20 m) and the deeper coral refugia, ensuring the long-term resilience of the entire Pemba marine ecosystem.

2.2 Coral Reef Monitoring

2.2.1 Introduction

To support the proposal to develop the new MCAs, WCS conducted coral reef monitoring to establish an ecological baseline for the area using a combination of benthic substrate assessment, coral recruitment, photo quadrat data collection, fish abundance, fish biomass, sea urchin density, and invertebrate abundance, which are part of WCS's annual scientific monitoring. Reef monitoring is required to assess the state of the ecosystem and, importantly, the resources that local communities depend on. Having ecological baselines enables monitoring of environmental changes and is key to understanding and managing an area.

Figure 2.10: WCS scuba diver completing a LIT transect for benthic cover.

2.2.2 Methodology

In cooperation with employees of the Department of Marine Conservation (DMC) under the Ministry of Fisheries and Blue Economy (MoBEF), the Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS) Tanzania Marine Program staff conducted an ecological baseline survey from January 26th to February 9th, 2024 (which also served as a pre-bleaching survey) and a set of follow-up surveys at select sites after the 2024 bleaching event, September 10-13, 2024. Additional surveys were conducted from August 16th to August 24th, 2025, to record the baseline and monitor changes over time at the coral restoration site. These surveys form the basis of the results in this section. Surveys were led by Pagu Julius and a team member from the WCS Tanzania Marine Program field expedition, with staff from the Department of Marine Conservation, Zanzibar. A total of ten locations were surveyed: Pangapunge Inner South, Pangapunge Outer South, Pangapunge Inner North, Pangapunge Outer North, Mshame Inner South, Mshame Inner North, Mshame Outer South, Mshame Outer North, Kojani, and Vumawimbi in the

northern region. All were within the proposed Marine Protected Area in East Pemba.

Table 2.3: Sites surveyed in the East of Pemba, going from North to South.

Site	Lat (S)	Long (E)	Exposure	Data Collected	Survey Date
Pangapunge Inner South reef	4.84487	39.75861	Semi Exposed	Benthic cover, Biomass, Invertebrate & Urchin count	16/8/2025
Pangapunge Outer South reef	4.84542	39.75801	Semi Exposed	Benthic cover, Biomass, Invertebrate & Urchin count	17/8/2025
Pangapunge Outer North reef	4.83491	39.75825	Semi Exposed	Benthic cover, Biomass, Invertebrate & Urchin count	19/8/2025
Pangapunge Inner North reef	4.84312	39.75737	Semi Exposed	Benthic cover, Biomass, Invertebrate & Urchin count	19/8/2025
Mshame Inner South reef	4.87495	39.70703	Semi Exposed	Benthic cover, Biomass, Invertebrate & Urchin count	20/8/2025
Mshame Inner North reef	4.87188	39.7057	Semi Exposed	Benthic cover, Biomass, Invertebrate & Urchin count	22/8/2025
Mshame Outer South reef	-4.8772	39.7042	Semi Exposed	Benthic cover, Biomass, Invertebrate & Urchin count	23/08/2025
Mshame Outer North reef	4.87252	39.70043	Semi Exposed	Benthic cover, Biomass, Invertebrate & Urchin count	24/08/2025
Vumawimbi	4.90243	39.70123	Semi Exposed	Benthic cover, Biomass, Invertebrate & Urchin count	3/2/2024 & 10/9/2024
Kojani	5.10795	39.87195	Exposed	Benthic cover, Biomass, Invertebrate & Urchin count	31/1/2024 & 13/9/2024

Transect-based surveys

The underwater fish visual census (UVC) was conducted using a 100 m by 5 m belt transect. Invertebrate abundance was measured using a 1.78 m radius circular quadrat, and substrate cover was measured using a 10 m Line Intercept Transect (LIT). For benthic substrate cover, six to nine LIT were used; for fish UVC, a minimum of two belt transects were conducted; and for invertebrate density, at least nine circular quadrats were used. For these surveys, results describe benthic cover, fish abundance and biomass, sea urchin density, and overall invertebrate status.

Coral recruits

A 1 m² quadrat was used to establish the baseline for coral recruits. All coral colonies with a maximum length of less than 10 cm were counted by genus into three size groups (0-2.5 cm, 2.5-5 cm, and 5-10 cm). To determine which size class each colony belonged to, the edge of the slates was marked with the three (3) size classifications. To determine coral recruits/juveniles, a total of 12 quadrats measuring 1 × 1 m² were employed for sampling at each site. Sampling intensity: two transects with six quadrats spaced every five meters, beginning at 0 m, 5 m, 10 m, 15 m, 20 m, and 25 m.

Photo-quadrants

A picture is taken at a height of 0.7–1 m above the substrate for each photo quadrat on both sides of a 25 m transect, yielding approximately 50 images. For analysis, 24 photo quadrats (photographs) per site are randomly selected for annotation. CoralNet is used to analyze images to characterize substrate

types, benthic composition, and genus-level coral cover. Photoquadrats are used online at the coral reef restoration site to monitor the restoration process and evaluate the success of coral transplantation.

Data Management

All monitoring data have been uploaded to <https://datamermaid.org>, an online repository freely available for collecting, organizing and analyzing coral reef data. The data is organized by survey type, and basic statistics are automatically calculated for each site and survey. Users can also download summary data directly from the platform.

2.2.3 Results

In summary, the surveyed sites comprise two oceanographic reef forms. The reefs off the east of Pemba are typically fringing coral reefs distributed in a narrow band along the East Coast. The main reef structure sits at 4-9 m during low tide, and the reef slope extends down to 25 m, eventually becoming a sandy substrate. This band lies within 50-100 m of the shore at most points, then drops to depths beyond the reach of photosynthetic corals. The East Coast is exposed to wind and weather events and is subject to stronger wave action more frequently than the more sheltered West Coast of Zanzibar. The north of Pemba, namely Msuka Bay, has an extended shelf that, in parts, extends more than 10 km from shore, reaching depths of <100 m. Hence, reef substrate in this area is more abundant and extensive. The area is northerly facing, hence somewhat sheltered from southerly weather systems and therefore less harsh than the east of Pemba.

In general, East Pemba reefs are strongly influenced by oceanographic factors that drive the ecological makeup. These areas experience continuous upwelling, and, as a result, the reefs are theoretically considered climate-resilient.

Benthic cover Hard coral cover varied significantly among the examined sites, with Vumawimbi that had the highest coral cover ($18.5 \pm 0.4\%$), followed by Mshame inner south ($9.84 \pm 1.87\%$) and Pangapunge inner north ($1.77 \pm 0.73\%$), as shown in Figure 2.11. This contrasts with coral cover measured through the Benthic Ecological Survey previously described, which is largely a consequence of the 2024 bleaching event. Coral cover was generally dominated by genera that are resistant to environmental stress, particularly temperature stress and anthropogenic pressure. Coral cover decreased as a result of the 2024 bleaching event. When comparing the reefs pre- and post-2024 bleaching event, Vumawimbi reef and Kojani were recorded at $37.5\% (\pm 4.7\%)$ and $35.5\% (\pm 3.1\%)$, respectively, before the bleaching event, and at $18.5\% (\pm 0.4\%)$ and $6.75\% (\pm 0.2\%)$, respectively, after the bleaching event. Thus, the reefs were considered functional with respect to coral cover prior to the bleaching event and unhealthy afterward. During the baseline survey, the following coral genera were observed, listed in alphabetical order: Acropora, Alveopora, Astreopora, Blastomussa, Diploastrea, Echinophyllia, Echinopora, Euphyllia, Favia, Favites, Fungia, Galaxea astreata, Galaxea fascicularis, Goniopora, Hydnothra, Millepora, Montastrea, Physogyra, Platygyra, Plerogyra, Pocillopora, Porites branching, Porites massive, Podabacia, Synarea, and Symphyllia, among others. Macroalgae, particularly Halimeda, Turbinaria, and Sargassum, were the dominant.

The coral reef baseline was documented before the 2024 bleaching event at most sites, with a few sites surveyed a second time in 2025 for comparison and to document recovery. The overall hard coral

percentage cover was 37.1% ($\pm 4.2\%$) before bleaching and 17.9% ($\pm 3\%$) after bleaching. Sites sampled showed significant differences in percentage coral cover. Results for coral cover before bleaching ranged from 31 ($\pm 2\%$) at Chambani Reef to 44 ($\pm 4\%$) at Shamiani. Similarly, before bleaching, coral cover was highest at Shamiani, while the lowest was recorded at Furaha Reef. Coral cover was generally dominated by genera resistant to environmental stress, including fishing disturbance, mainly *Porites* sp and a few *Acropora* sp, *Porites* branching species, among others. During the baseline surveys, the following coral genera were observed, listed in alphabetical order: *Acropora*, *Alveopora*, *Astreopora*, *Blastomussa*, *Diploastrea*, *Echinophyllia*, *Echinopora*, *Euphyllia*, *Favia*, *Favites*, *Fungia*, *Galaxea astreata*, *Galaxea fascicularis*, *Goniopora*, *Hydnophora*, *Millepora*, *Montastrea*, *Physogyra*, *Platygyra*, *Plerogyra*, *Pocillopora*, *Porites* branching, *Porites* massive, *Podabacia*, *Synarea*, and *Symphyllia*, among others. Macroalgae, particularly *Halimeda*, *Turbinaria*, and *Sargassum*, were the dominant.

Figure 2.11: Post-bleaching Hard Coral percentages for the surveyed sites in the north (top) and south (bottom).

Coral Recruitment Coral recruitment is a key indicator of reef recovery, and it was evaluated at selected sites in the north. High recruitment means more coral recruits settle and a greater likelihood

of an increase in coral population on that reef. Recruitment status at Mshame Reef and Pangapunge Reef was evaluated (Figure 2.12).

The coral recruitment data for the Mshame reef complex reveal a high degree of taxonomic and spatial variability, which is essential for understanding the regenerative potential of the proposed Marine Conservation Areas. By analyzing the density of juvenile colonies across three size classes (0–2.5 cm, 2.5–5 cm, and 5–10 cm), we can identify which reef sectors are currently acting as the strongest recruitment sinks.

The outer reef sites generally exhibit higher recruitment densities compared to the inner lagoonal sites, likely due to increased larval supply from oceanic currents and more favorable hard-bottom substrates.

- **Mshame Outer North:** This site represents the most productive recruitment zone identified. It is heavily dominated by *Hydnopora*, which shows an exceptional peak of approximately 13 colonies per m^2 in the 2.5–5 cm size class. Other significant contributors include *Galaxea fascicularis* and *Diploastrea*, which show consistent recruitment across all three size classes, indicating sustained settlement over multiple seasons.
- **Mshame Outer South:** While the total density is lower than the northern sector, the Outer South reef displays a more diverse recruitment profile. *Porites Massive* is the dominant genus here, particularly in the 2.5–5 cm range. Notably, *Echinopora* and *Pocillopora* show a healthy distribution of the smallest size class (0–2.5 cm), suggesting very recent successful settlement events.
- **Mshame Inner North:** The inner north reef is characterized by a high abundance of *Galaxea fascicularis* and *astrea*. *Galaxea Red* shows a strong presence in the 2.5–5 cm class, while *Galaxea Green* dominates the larger 5–10 cm juvenile class. This shift toward larger juveniles may indicate a stable environment where initial settlers have higher survival rates.
- **Mshame Inner South:** This sector shows the lowest overall taxonomic diversity among recruits. *Synareaea* is the standout performer, reaching nearly 8 colonies per m^2 in the 2.5–5 cm class. The presence of *Porites Massive* and *Echinopora* is much more limited here compared to the outer reef sites.

The prevalence of the 2.5–5 cm size class across almost all sites and species is a positive indicator of reef resilience. It suggests that once coral larvae successfully settle (the 0–2.5 cm phase), they have a high probability of surviving the initial post-settlement mortality period. The "recruitment hotspots" identified in the Outer North, particularly for *Hydnopora*, should be viewed as high-priority "nursery" zones. From a management perspective, the fact that different genera dominate different reef sectors (e.g., *Hydnopora* in the Outer North vs. *Synareaea* in the Inner South) suggests that the proposed MCAs will protect a diverse genetic and taxonomic portfolio. Ensuring that these juvenile-heavy areas are protected from physical damage, such as trampling or destructive fishing gear, is critical to ensuring they mature into the adult "coral gardens" that drive the wider ecosystem's health.

Fish Abundance and Biomass The survey results indicate that fish abundance and biomass in the Pemba region are influenced by a combination of management interventions and localized environmental factors (Figure 2.13). In the northern part, the impact of community-led conservation is evident

Figure 2.12: Recruitment surveys for Mshame inner and outer reef in the northern Pemba.

at Vumawimbi Reef. As a site with an active community closure, Vumawimbi exhibited the highest ecological performance, with an abundance of 880 ± 2 fish/ha and a biomass of 924 ± 24 kg/ha. These values are consistent with a site with zero or very limited fishing [McClanahan et al., 2011]. This was followed by Kojani, where strong currents and deeper bathymetry likely support higher fish abundance (634 ± 15 fish/ha) and biomass (469 ± 68 kg/ha). However, at the remaining eight sites, fish biomass fell below the critical ecological threshold of 300 kg/ha — a level often cited as the minimum required to maintain reef health and functionality. The lowest values were recorded at Mshame Outer South Reef, which supported only 67 ± 16 fish/ha and a meager biomass of 15.43 ± 4.99 kg/ha. Taxonomically, the assemblages were diverse, featuring 23 families including Acanthuridae, Lutjanidae, and Serranidae, with Labridae, Chaetodontidae, Pomacentridae, and Scaridae emerging as the dominant groups. A similar pattern of spatial variability was observed in the southern sector. Furaha Reef demonstrated the highest productivity in the southern region, with a biomass of 504 ± 147 kg/ha and a fish count of 1150 ± 171 fish/ha. In contrast, Kuku Reef showed significantly lower values, with biomass dropping to 95 ± 17 kg/ha and abundance to 209 ± 10 fish/ha. The southern sites shared a similar taxonomic breadth with the north, though the dominant families shifted slightly to include Acanthuridae and Haemulidae alongside Scaridae and Labridae.

Sea Urchins Density The survey results for sea urchin density highlight significant spatial heterogeneity across the Pemba coastline, with taxonomic composition largely dominated by a single resilient

Figure 2.13: Results from fish biomass surveys in northern (top) and southern (bottom) Pemba.

species (Figure 2.14).

The northern sites exhibited the most extreme variations in abundance. *Echinostrephus molaris* emerged as the dominant species across nearly all locations. This small, rock-boring urchin is ecologically adapted to high-energy environments, utilizing small depressions in the reef framework to seek refuge from strong currents and predation. The highest density was recorded at Kojani, which supported 52 individuals per 10 m², all of which were *E. molaris*. In stark contrast, Vumawimbi Reef stood out as a biological anomaly with zero urchins recorded during the survey period. Beyond echinoids, the macroinvertebrate census identified a diverse community of crabs, gastropods, starfish, bivalves, and sea cucumbers within the 10 m² transects.

Similar to the north, the southern sites were characterized by the prevalence of *E. molaris*, though the community structure featured a broader assembly of Diadematidae. Four distinct species were documented: *Diadema setosum*, *Diadema savignyi*, *Echinothrix diadema*, and *Echinostrephus molaris*. While *E. molaris* remains the primary occupant of the reef matrix, the presence of the long-spined

Diadema species indicates areas of varying structural complexity and grazing pressure.

Figure 2.14: Sea urchins statistics for the Northern (top) and Southern (bottom) sites.

Invertebrate Abundance Total invertebrate enumeration was conducted only at sites where coral-reef restoration will be implemented to record changes in invertebrate populations over time. This effort recorded invertebrates of both ecological and economic importance. Results revealed variation among surveyed sites. Echinostrephus molaris sea urchin was the dominant species, with an average of 1.29 per 10 m² across sites, followed by crabs at 0.8 per 10 m².

2.2.4 Conclusions

The current survey has successfully established a multi-taxa ecological baseline, providing a high-resolution snapshot of the marine environment. This baseline encompasses critical indicators of reef health, including benthic substrate composition, fish abundance and biomass, and the abundance and diversity of key invertebrate indicator species, notably sea urchins. To ensure long-term data utility and transparency, all photo-quadrat images have been processed and uploaded to CoralNet for

future automated feature analysis, while raw ecological datasets have been archived on the open-access platform, Mermaid.org. This digital infrastructure facilitates standardized data sharing and global comparison, reinforcing the scientific rigor of the regional monitoring program.

The analysis revealed significant spatial variation across the surveyed sites, highlighting a mosaic of ecological conditions—from high-integrity "coral gardens" to degraded rubble zones. These findings provide the essential evidence base to support the formal designation and strategic design of the proposed Marine Conservation Areas in East Pemba. By identifying specific biodiversity hotspots and areas under environmental stress, the survey enables managers to implement targeted interventions that maximize conservation impact. To build upon this baseline, subsequent and regular monitoring is recommended at the established sites. Consistent data collection will be vital for tracking ecosystem progress, assessing the efficacy of management regimes, and adaptively managing the resources that remain central to the livelihoods and food security of local communities.

2.3 Mangrove Ecosystem Surveys

2.3.1 Introduction

This report presents findings prepared by the WIOMN from mangrove assessments, change analyses, and mapping in target communities, thereby identifying degraded and restorable sites. Socio-economic surveys, also conducted, are documented separately to ensure socially inclusive and sustainable restoration efforts that respect local realities and foster community trust.

Mangrove resource assessment and mapping were conducted to determine the status of forest structure, composition, and aboveground biomass stock; and to assess drivers, rates, and patterns of degradation. This is important for determining the best options to facilitate active mangrove restoration in the two project sites. The assessment facilitates validation of the availability of the targeted 150 ha for active planting.

Accordingly, this study had the following specific objectives:

- Conduct mangrove forest resource assessment through an inventory to determine forest structure, composition, and above-ground biomass
- Mapping of mangrove forest cover change, determining the rate and pattern of degradation, and identifying restorable areas

2.3.2 Methodology

Location and Sampling Sites

The study took places across sites in the Tanga region and the Pemba East. In Pemba, the study covered the Shehias of Mjananza, Tumbe, Kinowe, and Msuka in north and northeastern Pemba. Selection of these study villages and Shehias was based on a rapid mangrove cover analysis and field validation, as reported in a separate Scoping Study Report, in addition to expert knowledge of the areas.

Sampling Design and Data Collection

At each mangrove forest study site, circular sample plots of 10-meter radius (Figure 2.15) were laid out following the procedure recommended by J.B. and D. [2012]. Plot locations were randomly generated using a GIS-based machine-learning approach to ensure unbiased, representative sampling. High-resolution PlanetScope satellite imagery, combined with existing mangrove land cover maps, was used to identify mangrove-dominated areas within the selected villages. A study area boundary was defined, and non-mangrove areas were excluded. Within the defined extent, a stratified random sampling method was employed to account for spatial variability. Random sampling plots were generated using GIS. Each plot was spatially distributed with a minimum separation distance to prevent overlap and ensure even coverage across the maanalysis of mangrove cover and field validation, as reported in a separate Scoping Study Report, as well aanalysis of mangrove cover and field validation, as reported in a separate Scoping Study Report, as well ass natural regeneration potential by counting all saplings and seedlings with stem diameters less than 5 cm found within the sub-plot. This potential regenera-

Figure 2.15: Circular sampling plot design. Credit Rashid Ismail, WIOMN.

tion is excluded in forest biomass estimation because it does not provide a guaranteed full transition into a growing forest.

In Pemba, 21 plots were established, distributed as 10 for Mjananza, 5 for Msuka, 3 for Kinowe, and 3 for Tumbe Magharibi (Fig. 2.16).

Data Collection

Mangrove species composition, structure, distribution, and diversity were assessed using variables such as species identity, stem diameter at breast height (dbh), basal area (BA), relative frequency (RF), relative density (RD), relative basal area (RBA), and Importance Value Index (IVI). The relative indices reflect each species' overall contribution to the community, with RD and RBA increasing with the number of individuals, while RF is related to the number of plots in which a species was found. The IVI ranges from 0% to 300%, with tree species exceeding 50% considered dominant and most important, those with 10 – 50% of moderate importance, and those with less than 10% of low ecological importance or rare. These metrics indicate the significance or contribution of a particular mangrove species within the forest community. To determine these metrics, all standing trees in the 10 m radius sampling plot with $dbh > 5$ cm were identified by species and measured for circumference (cm) using a measuring tape, which was subsequently converted to dbh (cm). For the species *Rhizophora mucronata*, dbh was measured at 0.3 - 0.5 m above the highest prop root, as appropriate.

Vegetation Analysis Formulas

The formulas used for computing *RD*, *RBA*, *RF*, and *IVI* are:

$$RD = \left(\frac{\text{total individuals of a species}}{\text{total individuals of all species}} \right) \times 100$$

$$RBA = \left(\frac{\text{combined BA of a species}}{\text{total BA of all species}} \right) \times 100$$

$$RF = \left(\frac{\text{frequency of a species}}{\text{sum of all frequencies}} \right) \times 100$$

$$IVI = RD + RBA + RF$$

The basal area (BA) was calculated as $BA/Tree(m^2) = \frac{\pi \times (dbh)^2 \times 0.0001}{4}$ where π is 3.146, *dbh* is the diameter at breast height (cm), and 0.0001 is a constant used to convert the measured cm^2 into m^2 .

Table 2.4: Description of inventory plots, including GPS position and altitude.

Area	Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)	Description
Tumbe Mg	-4.940655	39.788037	31	The mangrove forest begins at this point
Mjananza	-5.03921	39.824452	18	Rice cultivation in proximity to the mangrove forest
Mjananza	-5.038914	39.825951	19	Livestock grazing near the mangrove forest
Mjananza	-5.040021	39.830552	18	Degraded area for firewood. Mixed old ones and second regeneration coming due to control measures
Mjananza	-5.04037	39.828496	17	This entire area represents second-generation mangrove growth
Mjananza	-5.040125	39.827506	17	Return of mangroves has allowed coconut trees to thrive by blocking seawater
Mjananza	-5.040802	39.826988	17	Dominant <i>Avicennia</i> species undergoing second-generation regeneration
Mjananza	-5.040432	39.82627	18	Large <i>Avicennia</i> trees were once prevalent in this area
Mjananza	-5.040098	39.826121	18	Second-generation area; large stumps indicate removal of first generation
Msuka	-4.909195	39.743372	19	Area designated for mangrove restoration activities
Kinowe	-4.931724	39.77509	34	Mangrove area designated for restoration initiatives
Kinowe	-4.939914	39.767073	32	Freshwater marsh near the mangrove forest, unsuitable for planting
Kinowe	-4.94442	39.758499	38	Location of the village leader's residence or meeting point
Tumbe Mg	-4.939499	39.777231	20	Ongoing mangrove restoration initiatives observed
Tumbe Mg	-4.939858	39.778615	19	Mangrove restoration activities are being implemented
Tumbe Mg	-4.941063	39.78181	19	Unsuccessful restoration; <i>Rhizophora</i> planted in sandy soil that became muddy
Tumbe Mg	-4.940653	39.781882	19	Area designated for ongoing restoration initiatives
Tumbe Mg	-4.940253	39.781403	17	<i>Rhizophora</i> species observed to be dying due to disease
Tumbe Mg	-4.940151	39.780997	18	Previously barren area, now successful healthy mangrove growth
Tumbe Mg	-4.94036	39.780737	20	Successful restoration efforts observed in Tumbe Mg
Tumbe Mg	-4.94114	39.780554	25	Area marks the beginning of the forest, presence of <i>Heritiera</i> species
Tumbe Mg	-4.939647	39.78762	24	Past damage to large forest; restoration since 2012 by local committee
Tumbe Mg	-4.93973	39.787618	27	Restoration initiatives underway in Tumbe Mg
Msuka	-4.912878	39.735773	34	Residence or meeting point of the village leader
Msuka	-4.909049	39.743368	25	Area where mangrove wood is used for boat construction
Msuka	-4.907505	39.743761	25	Starting point of the mangrove forest
Msuka ROI	-4.911875	39.74588	24	Specific location of interest showing significant degradation
Msuka	-4.913336	39.746598	23	Stunted mangrove trees and signs of degradation
Msuka	-4.914061	39.747321	21	Severely degraded due to charcoal production; bird habitat
Msuka	-4.914208	39.747498	19	Larger trees affected by charcoal; only new growth remaining
Msuka	-4.914569	39.748207	18	Waterway supplying forest; evidence of coral and tree cutting
Msuka	-4.9148	39.748563	16	Natural <i>Avicennia</i> regeneration; stunted trees from selective cutting
Msuka	-4.913078	39.747594	14	Stunted <i>Avicennia</i> trees degraded due to charcoal production
Msuka	-4.912677	39.746173	14	Presence of <i>Lumnizera</i> and stunted mangrove species observed
Msuka	-4.912319	39.746082	14	Significant degradation observed in this section
Msuka	-4.91169	39.745956	14	Stunted mangrove trees and overall degradation
Msuka	-4.911486	39.745681	14	Stunted trees and signs of degradation in the forest
Msuka	-4.911044	39.746203	14	Degradation evident due to firewood and coral extraction

Figure 2.16: Inventory plots distribution for Pemba study sites. Left Pemba north Msuka bay. Right Pemba Middle East.

The total basal area for each plot was then calculated by summing the basal area of all trees within that plot. The formula for basal area per tree and total stand basal area are as *Total Stand Basal Area* (m^2/ha) = $\frac{\text{Sum of basal area of all trees} \times \sum P}{0.03146}$ where 0.03146 is plot size in hectare and $\sum P$ is the sum of plots (in this case 21). Stem *dbh* measurements, as described in the previous section, were used to estimate above-ground biomass (*AGB*) and below-ground biomass (*BGB*) for each individual tree using allometric equations in Table 2.6 recommended by Njana et al. [2018]. The mean wood density (ρ) for each species was obtained from the Global Wood Density Database. Plot-level *AGB* and *BGB* were calculated by summing individual tree estimates and then scaled to per-hectare values ($Mgha^{-1}$). Total tree biomass (*TB*) was determined by combining the *AGB* and *BGB* estimates.

Table 2.6: Allometric models recommended for estimation of *AGB* ($kg\ tree^{-1}$) and *BGB* ($kg\ tree^{-1}$) for mangroves of Tanzania [Njana et al., 2018].

Biomass Component	Model type	Species	Model
Above-Ground Biomass ($kg\ tree^{-1}$)	Common		$AGB = 0.25128 \times dbh^{2.24034}$
	Species-specific	<i>Avicennia marina</i>	$AGB = 0.25128 \times dbh^{2.24351}$
		<i>Sonneratia alba</i>	$AGB = 0.25128 \times dbh^{2.21727}$
		<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i>	$AGB = 0.25128 \times dbh^{2.26026}$
Below-Ground Biomass ($kg\ tree^{-1}$)	Common		$BGB = 1.4204 \times dbh^{1.59666}$
	Species-specific	<i>Avicennia marina</i>	$BGB = 1.4204 \times dbh^{1.44260}$
		<i>Sonneratia alba</i>	$BGB = 1.4204 \times dbh^{1.65760}$
		<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i>	$BGB = 1.4204 \times dbh^{1.68979}$

Mangrove regeneration and degradation assessment

The potential for mangrove natural regeneration was assessed by counting and identifying by species all seedlings and saplings in each sub-plot of 2 m radius and computing and presenting on a ha basis. To assess degradation, all stumps found within the 10 m radius sampling plot were counted and identified by species, and computed and presented on a per ha basis.

Mapping of mangrove extent and cover change analysis

Mapping and cover-change analysis used high-resolution Sentinel-2 and Landsat imagery, complemented by Sentinel-1 SAR data, to improve accuracy in cloud-affected areas. The Random Forest algorithm, implemented via the Google Earth Engine (GEE) Python API, was used for supervised classification. Input features included vegetation indices such as NDVI, NDWI, and mangrove-specific indices (e.g., Mangrove Index and Combined Mangrove Recognition Index), as well as spectral-temporal metrics (STMs) that capture phenological variation. Post-classification filtering steps refined the results, including majority filtering, size thresholding, and elevation masking using SRTM data. Expert

knowledge and field observations from the sampling exercise were used to manually correct misclassified areas, particularly where mangroves were spectrally similar to other land covers, such as coconut plantations.

Change analysis between 1990 and 2023 was conducted using Landsat-derived Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI) composites. Yearly NDMI time series data (1990–2023) were processed in GEE, and the LandTrendr algorithm was used to detect changes in mangrove cover. The algorithm identified temporal breakpoints in the NDMI time series, indicating vegetation loss or recovery. The detected changes were masked by the classified mangrove extents for 1990 and 2023 to ensure accuracy. Post-analysis filtering removed pseudo-changes arising from differences in spatial and spectral resolution between the Sentinel and Landsat datasets.

Drivers of mangrove cover change

During the field operations described in the previous section, potential and empirical anthropogenic and natural drivers of mangrove cover change and degradation were identified. The information collected was used to inform the mapping exercise described in the previous section to determine the need for and options of restoration measures. Different degradation scenarios were captured using a digital camera.

2.3.3 Results

Species Composition and Distribution

Overall, the Pemba area was more species-rich than the Tanga area. Of the 10 mangrove species reported to occur in Tanzania (Mangora et al. 2016), eight were identified in the Pemba study area, namely *Avicennia marina*, *Rhizophora mucronata*, *Sonneratia alba*, *Bruguiera gymnorrhiza*, *Ceriops tagal*, *Lumnitzera racemosa*, *Heritiera littoralis*, and *Xylocarpus granatum* (Table 22). *Rhizophora mucronata* was the most common species overall (40%), followed by *A. marina* (27%), *S. alba* (19%), and *C. tagal* (11%). At specific sites, Tumbe and Kinowe had higher proportions of *R. mucronata* (70.5% and 48.5%, respectively), whereas Mjananza had more *A. marina* (60.7%), and Msuka had more *S. alba* (41.6%). *Lumnitzera racemosa* was the least common at all sites. In the Tanga study area, only five of the 10 mangrove species were recorded, with *R. mucronata*, *A. marina*, and *C. tagal* the most common at 56%, 20%, and 18%, respectively, followed by *S. alba* (4%) and *B. gymnorrhiza* (3%). At specific sites, Maere had *R. mucronata* at over 50%, followed by *A. marina* at 20% and *C. tagal* at 10%, whereas Geza-Kirare had *C. tagal* at 25% and *A. marina* at 19%. *S. alba* and *B. gymnorrhiza* were the least common at all sites.

Average diameter, density and basal area Table 2.8 summarizes forest structural traits of the studied mangrove forest sites. Overall, average stem diameter ranges from 6.4 – 9.8 cm, stem density is 1385 – 1926 stems ha⁻¹ and basal area ranges from 9.4 – 15.3 m² ha⁻¹. These values are low compared to the global and regional reference data from well-developed mangrove forest [Kairo et al., 2001, Bosire et al., 2003a]. This suggests that Pemba mangrove forests are recovering from recent degradation but remain on a fairly good recovery trajectory.

Table 2.7: Percentage mangrove species composition and distribution at the study sites. Source: Field data collected in 2024. Note: - indicates absence of the species at the site.

Mangrove species	Kinowe	Mjananza	Tumbe	Msuka	Average
Rhizophora mucronata	48.5	13.1	70.5	28.3	40.1
Avicennia marina	21.5	60.7	1.3	23.7	26.8
Ceriops tagal	26.2	14.7	0.7	3.5	11.3
Sonneratia alba	-	8.6	26.8	41.6	19.3
Lumnitzera racemosa	0.4	0.8	-	-	0.3
Heritiera littoralis	3.0	-	-	-	0.7
Xylocarpus granatum	-	0.3	-	-	0.1
Bruguiera gymnorhiza	0.4	1.8	0.7	3.5	1.6

Diameter distribution Stem diameter distribution across all sites in Pemba (Figure 2.17) indicates that Pemba's mangroves exhibited an inverted J-shape, with many small-diameter trees and fewer large, old trees. This pattern is characteristic of natural, uneven-aged forests and indicates a potentially healthy, regenerating population structure [Rubin et al., 2006]. This contrasts with the expected reverse J-shaped distribution, characteristic of disturbed forest stands under perceived human pressures, in which old trees face cutting pressure. The observed patterns for Pemba confirms that these forests are on a good trajectory for recovery, with past degradation substantially reduced, albeit some residual human pressures persist.

Figure 2.17: Stem diameter distribution in Pemba study area.

Table 2.8: Average DBH, Density, and Basal Area per Site and Species

Site	Species	Average DBH (cm)	Density (stems ha ⁻¹)	BA (m ² ha ⁻¹)
Kinowe	A. marina	6.7	405.8	1.6
	B. gymnorhiza	7.4	8	0
	C. tagal	5.8	493.3	1.4
	H. littoralis	20.6	55.7	2
	L. racemosa	7	8	0
	R. mucronata	7	915	4.3
	Overall		9.1	1885.7
Mjananza	A. marina	7.5	1168	9
	B. gymnorhiza	9	35	0.3
	C. tagal	4.9	283.3	0.6
	L. racemosa	6.9	15.9	0.1
	R. mucronata	7.5	251.4	2
	S. alba	11.1	165.5	2.1
	X. granatum	5.9	6.4	0
	Overall		7.6	1925.5
Msuka	A. marina	8.5	326.2	2.5
	B. gymnorhiza	11.8	47.7	0.7
	C. tagal	8	47.7	0.2
	R. mucronata	12.5	389.9	8.3
	S. alba	8	572.9	3.5
	Overall		9.8	1384.5
Tumbe	A. marina	6.7	21.2	0.1
	B. gymnorhiza	4	10.6	0
	C. tagal	3.9	10.6	0
	R. mucronata	6.5	1113.9	6.8
	S. alba	10.8	424.4	5.9
	Overall		6.4	1580.7

Above- and Below-ground Biomass and Carbon

R. mucronata had higher values of AGB and BGB, along with corresponding AGC and BGC, except at Mjananza, where A. Marina had higher values (Table 2.9). Nonetheless, the observed values remained below the expected reference values for healthy, well-developed mangrove forests reported from different regions. Although reported global biomass values vary by region and by forest characteristics such as species composition, stand age, and hydrological setting, global syntheses and site-level studies report ranges of 150–300 Mg ha⁻¹, with exceptional riverine and estuarine stands exceeding 400–500 Mg ha⁻¹. These figures are widely accepted in mangrove ecology and carbon accounting to

inform management prescriptions. The low values at the project sites further confirm that these forests are in a post-degradation succession.

Table 2.9: Biomass and Carbon Stock by Site and Species

Site	Species	AGB (Mg ha ⁻¹)	BGB (Mg ha ⁻¹)	AGC (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	BGC (Mg C ha ⁻¹)
Kinowe	A. marina	8.2	2.7	3.8	1.1
	B. gymnorhiza	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0
	C. tagal	7.3	3.6	3.4	1.4
	H. littoralis	13.9	3.1	6.4	1.2
	L. racemosa	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0
	R. mucronata	25.0	11.6	11.5	4.5
	Total	54.8	21.2	25.2	8.2
Mjananza	A. marina	59.3	10.6	27.3	4.2
	B. gymnorhiza	1.7	0.6	0.8	0.2
	C. tagal	2.6	1.5	1.2	0.6
	L. racemosa	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.1
	R. mucronata	13.3	4.4	6.1	1.7
	S. alba	12.5	4.4	5.7	1.7
	X. granatum	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total	90.0	21.7	41.4	8.5	
Msuka	A. marina	15.0	3.3	6.9	1.3
	B. gymnorhiza	4.3	1.2	2.0	0.5
	C. tagal	1.3	0.6	0.6	0.2
	R. mucronata	62.7	16.4	28.8	6.4
	S. alba	19.2	8.5	8.8	3.3
Total	102.5	29.9	47.2	11.7	
Tumbe	A. marina	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.1
	B. gymnorhiza	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
	C. tagal	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
	R. mucronata	46.9	15.5	21.6	6.0
	S. alba	36.6	11.7	16.8	4.6
Total	84.0	27.4	38.7	10.7	

Degradation

The levels of mangrove forest degradation were determined using stump counts, which represent cutting pressures (Table 2.10). Accordingly, sites in Pemba were more degraded than those in Tanga. The Tumbe site was the most degraded, with up to 3775 stumps/ha, followed by Msuka with 1174 stumps/ha, Mjananza with 920 stumps/ha, and the least degraded, Kinowe, with 390 stumps/ha. The species R. mucronata, C. tagal, A. marina, and S. alba were the most affected and therefore targeted for restoration. According to [Bosire et al., 2003b], the high abundance of C. tagal and R. mucronata stumps explains their known use for construction, poles, and fuel in East African coastal communities.

Table 2.10: Stump Density and Distribution by Shehia

Shehia/Village	Species	Stump density (Stumps ha ⁻¹)	% Distribution
Kinowe	A. marina	7.96	2.04
	C. tagal	119.35	30.61
	H. littoralis	127.31	32.65
	R. mucronata	135.27	34.70
	Overall	389.88	
Mjananza	A. marina	254.61	27.68
	B. gymnorhiza	22.28	2.42
	C. tagal	591.98	64.36
	L. racemosa	6.37	0.69
	R. mucronata	44.56	4.84
Overall	919.80		
Msuka	A. marina	254.61	22.07
	B. gymnorhiza	31.83	2.76
	R. mucronata	366.01	31.72
	S. alba	501.27	43.45
Overall	1153.72		
Tumbe	C. tagal	954.80	25.50
	R. mucronata	2631.02	70.26
	S. alba	159.13	4.25
Overall	3744.95		

Regeneration Potential

The number of seedlings and saplings per ha, presented in Table 2.11, indicate the potential for natural regeneration and self-sustenance of the mangrove sites. Overall, Mjananza and Kinowe had high numbers of seedlings per ha, whereas Tumbe had a high number of saplings per ha. Based on these values, the species R. mucronata and A. marina were the most promising for natural regeneration and for shaping the future of the forests, particularly regarding potential shifts in species composition where they occur. Overall, there were fewer saplings than seedlings, indicating a poor transition to saplings and suggesting potential challenges in recruitment or survival that require further study to establish, beyond the scope of the present assessment.

Mangrove Forest Cover Change

An analysis of mangrove cover change in the study sites of Pemba revealed that mangrove forests covered 3,324.88 ha in the 1990s. By 2023, this had decreased to 2,605.52 ha, representing a 25.5% loss in mangrove cover. Over the past 33 years, 127.52 ha of mangroves were gained, reducing the net loss of mangrove cover to 22%, translating to an annual loss of 21.7 ha and a rate of 0.6%. However,

Table 2.11: Sapling Counts and Regeneration Density

Shehia/Village	Species	Count	Saplings/ha	% Distribution
Kinowe	R. mucronata	26	206.87	57.78
	C. tagal	19	151.18	42.22
	Overall	45.00	358.05	
Mjananza	A. marina	55	175.05	25.82
	R. mucronata	78	248.25	36.62
	C. tagal	80	254.61	37.56
	Overall	213	677.91	
Msuka	R. mucronata	43	342.14	100
	Overall	43	342.14	
Tumbe	R. mucronata	94	997.24	74.60
	C. tagal	32	339.49	25.40
	Overall	126	1336.73	
Geza-Kirare	R. mucronata	35	111.39	68.63
	C. tagal	16	50.92	31.37
	Overall	51	162.32	
Maere	R. mucronata	21	60.76	60.00
	C. tagal	10	28.93	28.57
	B. gymnorrhiza	4	11.57	11.43

when the analysis was restricted to the past 10 years, results indicated an alarming annual loss of 3.1%, implying that most degradation has occurred during this period. Human activities, including mangrove harvesting for charcoal, construction materials, and agricultural expansion, are key drivers of this change. For example, field surveys in Tumbe observed extensive areas with clear evidence of mangrove cutting.

Drivers of Mangrove Cover Change

Mangrove Cutting During the field survey, evidence of mangrove cutting was observed in Tumbe and Kinowe on Pemba Island. Figure 40 shows a satellite image of the mangrove stands at these locations, along with a ground-level photograph taken at the site. Local knowledge suggests that cutting occurred approximately 5 to 8 years ago primarily for charcoal production, building poles, and timber. Although signs of natural regeneration are evident, ongoing fish-bait extraction poses a significant challenge to this process. To enhance recovery, the area requires human intervention, either through supportive measures to promote natural regeneration or through active planting efforts.

Fish bait extraction Excavation for the extraction of fish bait (polychaete worms) is common in both Tanga and Pemba, causing considerable degradation. To collect these worms, the fishermen dig

into the mangrove soil, cutting through pneumatophores and main roots and destabilizing the soil in the process.

Unsustainable salt production While solar salt production is considered a substantive activity that sustains livelihoods, mangrove forests suffer significantly if this approach is not adequately controlled. It entails clearing mangroves to make room and excavating large volumes of soil for dyke construction, both of which worsen mangrove conditions. Active salt making is a common activity at other areas, especially in the southeastern part of the island.

Mangrove area expansion for agriculture

Encroachment of agricultural activities, including rice farming, into mangrove areas was observed at Kinowe, Mjananza, Msuka, and Tumbe. This land-use challenge is also linked to emerging saltwater intrusion and undermines the critical role of mangroves in coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and habitat for a diversity of species.

2.3.4 Conclusions

The present mangrove resource assessment has revealed that the mangrove forests of the Pemba Channel seascape, comprising northern mainland Tanzania (Tanga) and northeastern Pemba Island, are under considerable anthropogenic pressure, resulting in structural degradation, biomass decline, and loss of forest cover, particularly over the last decade.

Despite the pressures, signs of natural regeneration and the dominance of ecologically resilient species such as *Rhizophora mucronata* and *Avicennia marina* indicate promising potential for recovery if targeted restoration and management measures are implemented. Forest structure analysis revealed inverted J-shaped diameter distributions, indicative of uneven-aged regenerating stands. However, biomass and carbon stocks remain below regional and global benchmarks for well-developed mangrove systems, underscoring the degraded but recoverable status of these forests.

Mangrove cover change analysis (1990–2023) confirms considerable net loss in Pemba East (22%), with accelerated deforestation in the last decade. Major drivers of degradation include wood extraction for charcoal and construction, agricultural encroachment, salt production, and fish-bait digging. These pressures are compounded by inadequate governance, weak enforcement, and limited community involvement in management.

This assessment establishes a scientific baseline to guide restoration by interested actors, providing a clear ecological basis for differentiated restoration strategies that reflect local forest structure, levels of degradation, and natural regeneration potential. It identifies priority sites for intervention, highlights key species for restoration, and demonstrates the urgent need for integrated ecological and community-based strategies to reverse mangrove degradation and enhance ecosystem resilience in the Pemba Channel seascape.

2.4 Fisheries Catch and Landing Site Monitoring

2.4.1 Introduction

This report focuses on the WCS-led monitoring program of landings of bony fishes and elasmobranchs (sharks and rays) in the Pemba East seascape. The monitoring program provides a scientific baseline for understanding extraction patterns and assessing the health of target reef fish stocks, as well as the impacts of fisheries on sharks and rays.

The successful management of the new Marine Conservation Area (MCA) in Pemba depends on a precise understanding of extraction patterns within its coral reef and pelagic ecosystems. In Zanzibar, where small-scale fisheries are the primary backbone of coastal livelihoods, increasing fishing pressure necessitates a transition from generalized observations to high-resolution monitoring. To provide this scientific baseline, WCS, with support from the Blue Action Fund, has established a dedicated monitoring program across four strategic landing sites in Pemba. This program monitors species-level catch data, documenting exact landing volumes, size frequencies, and gear-specific effort. The program provides the evidence base required to evaluate the health of target reef fish stocks.

An important component of this work is the monitoring of sharks and rays. As apex predators and high-value species, elasmobranchs are particularly vulnerable to overexploitation. Pemba Island also represents a critical component of the Important Shark and Ray Areas (ISRA) network due to its unique bathymetry and its role as a key migratory corridor and reproductive hub in the Western Indian Ocean, primarily for the scalloped hammerhead and various reef-associated rays. The Pemba Channel ISRA partially overlaps with the proposed Pemba East MCA, making it an important biological "hotspot" and thereby prioritizing the North Pemba MCA for international conservation efforts. The collected data are essential for developing targeted management measures—such as protected species lists and potential seasonal restrictions—that ensure the long-term persistence of Pemba's unique marine biodiversity. Additionally, the report will cover a study using baited remote underwater video (BRUV) to assess the abundance and diversity of sharks and rays in their natural habitat, providing a complementary ecological perspective to the landing-site data.

The following sections are divided into two parts: the first focuses on the catch monitoring program for *bony fish*, the primary target species for the MCA, while the second provides a detailed analysis of *elasmobranchs*, given their conservation importance and vulnerability to fishing pressure.

2.4.2 Bony Fish Landings Monitoring Methods

The monitoring program implemented by WCS, with support from the Blue Action Fund, uses a standardized approach compatible with the Government's catch data collection efforts and has been developed in collaboration with partners and stakeholders over the years. The data collection protocol is used across several sites in Zanzibar and on the Mainland, specifically in Pemba East, at Msuka, Mtangani, Mvumoni Furaha, and Kojani.

Field operations are conducted by trained community enumerators, selected for each landing site in collaboration with Government authorities and communities. The data collection started in October 2023 as is currently ongoing. Data collection in Msuka started in 2022. To ensure a representative sample of fishing effort while maintaining data quality, enumerators conducted site visits three days per week, synchronized with peak landing times. All data were recorded digitally using the

KoboCollect platform, allowing for real-time validation and reducing transcription errors common in paper-based systems. All data are displayed in near-real time on a dashboard accessible to the Government and stakeholders, enabling real-time data visualization and analysis: <https://dashboard-uaps.onrender.com>.

During data collection, a few recommendations are passed to the data collectors,

- Data collectors need to be on site before the landing of the boats to ensure that they can capture all the data related to the fishing trip, including the catch and effort data.
- Data collection must happen at the landing location and not the fish market to make sure that the catch is linked to the right boat and fishing trip, which is important for the analysis of the catch and effort data.
- All catch has to be recorded, including the catch that is not sold at the market, which is important for the analysis of the catch and effort data. For this reason, the survey is designed to be rapid, classifying the catch into broad taxonomic groups and weighing the catch using a scale. This allows the data collectors to capture all the catch data without missing any important information.

Several pieces of information are collected on catch and effort data, which are important for the analysis. These include:

- **Effort and Spatial Metrics:** Vessel type (e.g., *Ngalawa*, *Mtumbwi*, *Mashua*), gear category (e.g., handlines, traps, gillnets, spear guns), fishing ground name, habitat type (Reef, Pelagic, Seagrass), and depth.
- **Catch Composition:** Total weight of the catch (measured using 25kg or heavy-duty balances), categorized by major groups including reef fish, small pelagics, and mollusks/crustaceans.

2.4.3 Sharks and Rays Landings Monitoring Methods

The protocol is identical to that used for bony fish, with some specificities related to the biology of sharks and rays. Data collection is conducted by trained community enumerators at landing sites and markets, with a focus on shark and ray landings. The data collection began in October 2023 and continues. Data collection in Msuka started in 2022. The main difference is in the type of data collected, which is more detailed for sharks and rays, given their conservation importance and vulnerability to fishing pressure, and the data processing, which requires species identification and validation by experts, which is not the case for bony fish.

Given their status as Endangered, Threatened, and Protected (ETP) species, a rigorous sub-protocol was applied to all shark and ray landings. In addition to standard catch metrics, the following biological and morphological data were collected:

- **Morphometrics:** Sex, total weight, and precise length measurements, including for sharks, total length, fork length, sex, and maturity, were recorded. For rays and sharks, disc length, disc width, sex, and maturity were recorded.

- **Photographic Evidence:** A mandatory set of five diagnostic photographs (Lateral, Dorsal, Ventral, and fins) was captured for each specimen to facilitate remote expert verification and species identification.
- **Fishery Interaction:** Records of whether elasmobranchs were the primary target or incidental bycatch, and the frequency of such catches.
- **Gear-Specific Data:** Detailed information on the fishing gear used, including type, mesh size, and deployment method, to analyze gear-specific impacts on shark and ray populations. Same information as for bony fishes.

To date, we records 2,589 records in Pemba East alone with a mean catch per record of 28.68 kg. A multi-tier validation process was employed: initial field identification was reviewed by the WCS Tanzania technical team, followed by final species verification by the WCS regional team. Once validated, the records in the database are updated with the correct species identification, and the data is made available for analysis.

Surveys in Pemba are conducted at the same locations as those for bony fishes, with the addition of the Chole market. Data collection ran from October 2023 to October 2025, yielding a total of 253 records and 5 species of landed fish.

2.4.4 Baited Remote Underwater Video (BRUV)

To complement the catch monitoring data, WCS implemented Baited Remote Underwater Video (BRUV) surveys to provide an independent, in-situ assessment of elasmobranch populations (Figure 2.18). This non-invasive methodology is essential for observing species that may not appear in traditional landings due to habitat depth, gear selectivity, or conservation status.

The survey was designed to establish a standardized ecological baseline across Zanzibar and the mainland Tanzanian coastline. In Pemba East, the survey targeted Msuka Bay, an area considered important, particularly for rays. Each BRUV unit consists of a pair of high-definition video cameras mounted in a stereo-configuration on a weighted steel frame. The "stereo" setup is calibrated prior to the field season to triangulate the exact 3D position of an animal, enabling highly accurate measurements of total length and disc width—data that is often difficult to obtain from moving animals in the wild.

To maintain a standardized sampling effort across all sites, the following protocol was observed:

- **Baiting:** A standardized bait canister (typically containing crushed oily fish like sardines) is attached to a PVC arm extending into the camera's field of view. This creates an odor plume that attracts predators and scavengers from the surrounding area.
- **Deployment:** The frame is lowered to the benthos and remains connected to a surface buoy for retrieval. Each site is sampled with 5 BRUVs, which are deployed at least 500 meters apart to ensure independent sampling.
- **Standardized Recording:** Once settled, the cameras are left recording for a continuous 45-minute "soak time." This duration is a global standard, ensuring that results from Tanzania are comparable to shark population data worldwide.

Figure 2.18: Deployment of a BRUV unit in Latham Island, Zanzibar. Photo credit: Dr. Ryan Daly/ORI.

- Retrieval: The frame is recovered, and data is logged with GPS coordinates, depth, and habitat type.

Videos are subsequently analyzed in the laboratory using specialized software that enables frame-by-frame review.

2.4.5 Results

Data collection ran from October 2023 to October 2025. Total catch was 37,451.73 kg, with 2,589 records and an average catch per record of 28.68 kg across all sites (Msuka, Mtangani, Mvumoni Furaha, and Kojani).

Bony Fish Landings

Figure 2.19 tracks the sampling effort of the enumerators at the four landing sites. A total of 4729 records were collected, with data collection that started in 2022 for Msuka and in 2024 for the other sites. The sampling effort is relatively consistent across the four sites.

Figure 2.20 shows the species composition of the landings by ecological functional group and by gear type. The dominance of Reef Fish in the landings underscores the high dependency of Pemba's coastal communities on coral reef ecosystems. This heavy reliance on a single ecological functional group highlights the vulnerability of local food security to reef degradation. The presence of Pelagics and Molluscs/Crustaceans suggests some degree of catch diversification, a positive indicator of community resilience. The diversity of gear types—ranging from Handlines and Traps to various Nets—reflects the multi-species nature of the fishery. Identifying which gears are most prevalent allows WCS to pinpoint

Figure 2.19: Sampling effort for monitoring of bony fishes across the four monitored sites in Pemba East.

potential management interventions, such as promoting more selective gears (e.g., specific trap mesh sizes) to reduce juvenile fish capture and minimize physical damage to the reef substrate.

Figure 2.21 shows the prevalence of traditional vessels like the Ngalawa and Mtumbwi confirms that the fishery remains largely artisanal and small-scale. However, the presence of more mechanized or larger vessels, such as Mashua or Fiberglass boats, indicates varying levels of range and effort. This data is essential for understanding how far from shore fishers are venturing and which habitats are under the most intense pressure. By cross-referencing effort with boat types, we can see which segments of the fleet are most active. A high number of trips by low-capacity vessels, such as the Mtumbwi, often indicates high pressure on nearshore habitats (seagrass and inner reefs). Conversely, higher effort from larger boats suggests a greater impact on offshore or fringing reef slopes.

Figure 2.22 illustrates the CPUE data, which is the most critical metric for assessing the status of the fish stocks. CPUE (kg/trip) acts as a proxy for fish abundance; a declining CPUE over time, despite constant or increasing effort, would be a strong signal of overfishing. Comparing CPUE across sites (Msuka, Mtangani, etc.) allows WCS to identify which areas are currently most productive and which may require urgent recovery measures under the new MCA framework.

Elasmobranchs Landings

Figure 2.23 tracks the sampling effort of the enumerators at the four landing sites. A total of 2842 records were collected, with data collection that started in 2022 for Msuka and in 2024 for the other sites. The sampling effort is relatively consistent across the four sites. A total of 62 species of sharks and rays were recorded in the landings, which is a significant number that highlights the biodiversity of elasmobranchs in the Pemba Channel seascape. This diversity underscores the area's importance as critical habitat for these species and justifies its designation as an ISRA. The high number of species also indicates that the local fisheries are impacting a wide range of elasmobranch taxa, which may have varying levels of vulnerability and conservation status. This information is crucial for developing targeted management measures that can address the specific needs of different species within the MCA framework.

The monitoring data (Figure 2.24) reveals a diverse elasmobranch assemblage dominated by the Silky shark (*Carcharhinus falciformis*), which accounts for the highest number of shark records. This is followed by other pelagic and reef-associated species such as the Pelagic thresher (*Alopias pelagicus*) and the Shortfin mako (*Isurus oxyrinchus*). Among the rays, the Blue-spotted maskray (*Neotrygon*

Figure 2.20: Species composition of shark and ray landings, along with their IUCN Red List status.

caeruleopunctata) is the most prevalent, with nearly 600 records, significantly outnumbering other ray species like the Maculate whipray (*Maculabatis ambigua*) and *Aetobatus ocellatus*. The high volume of *Carcharhinus falciformis* (classified as Vulnerable) and *Neotrygon caeruleopunctata* (classified as Near Threatened) highlights the significant pressure on these specific populations within the Zanzibar and Pemba fisheries.

The biological data presented in Figures 2.25 are critical for identifying essential fish habitats and nursery grounds within the Pemba seascape. Maturity data reveal a staggering proportion of immature (juvenile) individuals across nearly all recorded taxa. In sharks, immature specimens represent the vast majority of the catch, particularly for the dominant Silky shark (*Carcharhinus falciformis*), where over 140 of the recorded individuals were identified as immature. This trend is mirrored in the ray data, with the Blue-spotted maskray (*Neotrygon caeruleopunctata*) showing a massive peak in juvenile landings. Such high juvenile mortality at landing sites is a clear indicator that local fishing grounds overlap significantly with pupping or nursery areas. This supports the proposal for implementing targeted spatial or seasonal closures within specific zones of the North Pemba MCA to allow these populations to reach reproductive maturity.

Furthermore, sex-ratio data provide some insights into the population structure and potential sexual

Figure 2.21: Effort by type of vessel for monitoring of bony fishes across the four monitored sites in Pemba East.

segregation of elasmobranchs in this area. For most shark species, including the Silky shark and various Hammerheads (*Sphyrna* spp.), the landings show a relatively balanced distribution between males and females. However, the ray data shows more pronounced skews in certain species; for instance, the Blue-spotted maskray and Sharpnose stingray (*Telatyrygon zugei*) exhibit a higher frequency of females in the catch. Such skewed ratios can indicate the proximity of birthing grounds or sex-specific migratory routes through the Pemba East channels. Understanding these demographic signatures allows WCS to tailor management measures—such as gear restrictions or site-specific protection—to safeguard the most demographically significant segments of these vulnerable populations.

Results in Figure 2.26 provides a clear view of the drivers and methods of elasmobranch extraction in the region. For sharks, hook and line is the primary gear type, accounting for more than half of the landings at 51.2%, followed by gill nets of 6 inches (18.3%), and a combined 24.4% from 3-inch gill nets and ring nets. In the ray fishery, 3-inch gill nets are the dominant gear, responsible for 61.9% of landings, with 6-inch gill nets contributing another 29.6%. By identifying that small-mesh gill nets and hook-and-line fishing drive the majority of these landings, WCS can better focus gear-restricted zone proposals or selective fishing transitions with local Beach Management Units (BMUs).

The "Targeted vs. Bycatch" analysis reveals a high level of intentionality in the fishery for both

Figure 2.22: Catch Per Unit Effort (CPUE) for monitoring of bony fishes across the four monitored sites in Pemba East.

Figure 2.23: Effort data for shark and ray landings across the four monitored sites in Pemba East.

groups:

- Sharks: A significant 67.3% of landings are targeted, indicating a robust market demand and a specialized fishery.
- Rays: Similarly, 68.4% of ray landings are targeted, with only 31.6% classified as incidental bycatch.

These high targeting percentages—nearly 70% for both taxa—suggest that elasmobranchs are not merely accidental captures but are primary economic drivers for many fishers in the area. This underscores the urgent need for alternative livelihood interventions and species-specific management, as gear modifications alone may not be sufficient to reduce mortality when the intent to harvest is so high.

BRUVs

The survey took place around Pemba Island from March 19th to 28th, 2025. 11 sites (55 deployments) were done along Pemba East (Figure 2.27). A team of 8 participants, including WCS staff, MCA rangers, and community representatives. Surveys were conducted in the same areas as the coral reef surveys to assess whether these areas were also important areas for sharks and rays. The BRUVs were deployed at a depth range of 3 to 41 meters (Figure 2.28), targeting reef habitats where sharks and rays are most likely to occur. The data collected from the BRUV surveys will provide valuable insights into the abundance and diversity of elasmobranchs in their natural habitat, complementing the landing site data and informing management decisions for the MCA.

Figure 2.24: Species composition of shark and ray landings, along with their IUCN Red List status.

2.4.6 Conclusions

The WCS-led monitoring program in the Pemba East seascape establishes a critical scientific baseline for managing the new Marine Conservation Area and protecting its status as an ISRA. By tracking landings at four key sites and employing stereo-BRUV underwater video surveys, researchers have documented a high reliance of the community on reef-associated bony fishes and a diverse elasmobranch population comprising 62 species.

The findings highlight significant conservation concerns, particularly the high frequency of juvenile and globally threatened species—such as Hammerheads and Guitarfish—in local landings. This data indicates that active fishing grounds likely overlap with essential nursery habitats. By utilizing digital tools like KoboCollect for real-time tracking and expert-validated photographic evidence, the program provides the necessary evidence to implement targeted management strategies, including gear restrictions and seasonal closures, to ensure the long-term survival of Pemba’s unique marine biodiversity.

Figure 2.25: Sex ratios and maturity status of sharks and rays in the landings.

Figure 2.26: Gear used to catch sharks and rays and whether animals are targeted or not.

Figure 2.27: BRUV deployment location in Pemba East.

Figure 2.28: BRUV deployment depth in Pemba East.

2.5 Fishery Pattern Mapping (FPM)

2.5.1 Introduction

The primary goal of the Fishery Pattern Mapping (FPM) data was to measure fishing effort across gears and seasons. This work was done across the Tanzanian coastline and in Zanzibar, with a focus on the Pemba East seascape. The data collected through FPM are essential for understanding the spatial distribution of fishing activities, which are critical for informing management decisions and conservation strategies in the region.

The method we present here was developed by WCS as part of the Heshimu Bahari project and has been implemented in collaboration with local communities, government authorities, and other stakeholders. The approach is designed to be cost-effective and scalable, enabling the mapping of fishing grounds at the national level with limited resources and time. By collecting information on the shape and size of fishing grounds, we can create detailed maps of fishing effort and identify areas that may require targeted conservation measures. With respect to other approaches [Forero et al., 2017, Natsir et al., 2019, Behivoke et al., 2021], the method we present here does not rely on GPS trackers, which are relatively inexpensive, making it suitable for mapping fishing grounds at a national scale with limited resources and time. Similar approaches have been used before, even in Tanzania, but unlike previous efforts, in this work we are collecting information on the shape and size of fishing grounds, rather than on punctual locations, as was done in the past. Our approach allows us to transform this information into maps of fishing effort and potentially use the data to calculate catch and effort per area; an approach that has successfully been used to calculate reference points for reef fishers [McClanahan and Azali, 2020].

Results are helpful for showing how communities use the areas around Pemba East and for identifying areas of high fishing effort. This information is critical for managing the new MCA, as it can help identify areas that may require additional protection or management measures to ensure the sustainability of fisheries and the conservation of marine biodiversity in the region.

2.5.2 Methods

The fishery patterns mapping process is based on community consultations, using data collected from representatives of fishing communities to create maps of fishing grounds. The process involves several steps, starting with fishers identifying fishing grounds, followed by mapping these grounds using printed maps and Google Earth. Data are further analyzed to produce maps of relative fishing effort, disaggregated by gear and season. The activity was conducted with representatives from all communities in Zanzibar and mainland Tanzania to gather information on the location and characteristics of the fishing grounds.

list of gears in the national frame surveys for Mainland and Zanzibar (Table 2.12). During the fishery mapping, we also collected information on gleaning, seaweed farming, fish farming, sea cucumber farming, and crab fattening. This information is not presented in this report but is available in the data. Data on illegal gears, such as beach seines, is also collected, but is partial. It is also not presented in this report.

A facilitator led the group of fishermen in identifying their fishing grounds and drawing them on printed maps. The fishers are asked to give the name of the fishing ground, the perceived level of fishing effort (from 1 to 10) during each season (*kuzi* and *kaskazi*), whether they observe sharks, rays, marine mammals or sea turtles in that area (*yes* or *no* question), and whether they would consider the fishing ground for a permanent or a temporary closure (or none). This exercise continues till all known fishing grounds are mapped. The next step is to digitize the fishing grounds in Google Earth, a task performed by experienced personnel within the facilitator group. After digitizing the identified fishing grounds in Google Earth, the digital layers are projected onto a wall, and all fishers can suggest edits and modifications to the fishing ground polygons as needed. Once it is agreed that the polygons are correct, the grounds are saved as a KMZ file with a standardized name (Shehia_name of gear_name of fishing ground) for easy data analysis. In addition to identifying and mapping the fishing ground, other information related to seasonality, the number of fishing days, observations of endangered and protected species, and conservation preferences among fishermen was collected.

Field validation

While the FPM methodology for data collection with communities was found to produce consistent results across groups, it was also important to harmonize and validate the collected data. For every 20/30 communities surveyed, the results are summarized, harmonized, and re-presented to representatives from all surveyed communities. This last step allows us to harmonize fishing grounds further and address potential inconsistencies. A field verification step was sometimes needed to further resolve inconsistencies and confusion. In this step, fishing grounds with the same name and location are aggregated to reduce the total number of shapefiles.

The inconsistencies in the data can be due to two main problems. The first problem is that fishing grounds with the same name do not overlap, which may be due to different communities referring to the same fishing ground by different names or to different fishing grounds sharing the same name. The second problem is that fishing grounds with different names overlap, which may be due to different communities referring to the same fishing ground by different names, or to different fishing grounds with different names that overlap. The inconsistencies were identified using Python scripts, discussed with communities, and resolved.

To address the problem of non-overlapping fishing grounds sharing the same name, we first calculate this ratio for all such fishing grounds and flag those with low overlap for verification. It is possible that the different fishing grounds have the same name, for example, across different landscapes. The verification will instead focus on neighboring fishing grounds with the same name but low overlap. To address the second problem, the case of fishing grounds overlapping but with different names, we calculate the overlap ratio for all pairs of fishing grounds, select the largest overlaps (larger than 60%), and flag them when the names differ. It is possible that the same fishing ground is known by different names; the two names are appended into one.

In general, the goal of this step is to reduce potential errors and, as a final product, produce a map

of fishing grounds with clean, agreed-upon names among all fishers in the area.

Calculation of fishing effort

Once all data are compiled and validated, the dataset can be used to calculate fishing effort (F). Each shapefile is assigned the corresponding level of effort as reported by the fishers on a scale from 1 to 10, and scaled by its area in square kilometers. This is done to allow merging of the fishing effort reported by multiple communities. Effort ($f_{g,s}$) divided by area (A), and calculated for each gear g and season s can be summed for all overlapping fishing grounds so that fishing grounds that do not overlap contribute less to the overall effort than fishing grounds fished by multiple communities (Equation 2.1).

Figure 2.30: Example of the various shapefiles for a specific fishing ground. The boundaries of the same fishing ground vary as reported by fishers from different villages and fishing gears. The resulting fishing effort is the sum of the contributions of all fishing grounds.

Two coefficients are applied to the integration, one ($G(g)$) to account for the number of people fishing with each specific gear in various districts, and another ($S(s)$) to account for the fact that the seasons Kuzi and Kaskazi do not have the same duration. The coefficient $G(g)$ is calculated using data from the frame survey on the number of fishers per fishing gear across the various MPAs in Zanzibar and the districts on the Mainland of Tanzania (Table 2.12). The final effort should then take into account that some communities are larger than others and have an uneven distribution of fishing gear (Table 2.12).

$$F = \sum_s^{Ku, Ka} \sum_g f_{g,s} * G(g) * S(s) / A \quad (2.1)$$

The integration of fishing grounds also allows to minimize the potential errors derived from the

mapping of the fishing grounds. Different groups report the same fishing ground with varying boundaries. When stacked together, the fishing ground will show larger fishing effort in the areas of the fishing ground that are agreed upon by more fishers and less effort in the areas where only a few fishers report fishing (Figure 2.30).

$$S(s) = \begin{cases} \frac{7.5}{12}, & s = Apr - Nov \\ \frac{4.5}{12}, & s = Dec - Mar \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

The coefficient $S(s)$ is applied to account for the fact that fisherfolk reported different fishing effort across seasons, and that the two seasons have different duration (Equation 2.2). Kuzi and Kaskazi have a different duration. While the exact definitions can vary, generally, Kuzi goes from April to November (7.5 months), while Kaskazi goes from December to March (4.5 months).

Lastly, to make the data more suitable for the spatial prioritization tool, we further processed it by smoothing the raster files with a Gaussian filter to soften the sharp transitions between fishing grounds.

Table 2.12: Number of units of gear in each area

Gear Type	Gears in Pemba East	G(g)
Gill net	43	0.0005
Handline	4845	0.0519
Longline	37	0.0004
Ring net	48	0.0005
Trap	3223	0.0345
Spear	654	0.0070
Beach seine	107	0.0011
Shark net	7	0.0001
purse seine	654	0.0000

2.5.3 Results

The data can be used to study different aspects of the fishery, such as the distribution and seasonality of fishing effort across the seascape. In this section, we present some of the main results from the FPM data in Pemba East.

Fishing effort

For the creation of the MCA, the main interest of the FPM data is to identify areas of high fishing effort. This information can be used in a spatial prioritization model to identify areas that may require additional protection or management measures to ensure the sustainability of fisheries and the conservation of marine biodiversity in the region. In particular, areas with high fishing effort may require stricter regulations or enforcement to prevent overfishing.

Fishing effort is calculated as described in the previous section for the two seasons and for the totality of the fishing gears in Figure 2.31.

Figure 2.31: Total fishing effort for all gear and seasons.

Fishing effort is mainly coastal and is mainly associated with reef areas. The most intense fishing pressure within the proposed MPA is at its northernmost extent, in Msuka Bay. This area remains a high-priority zone for both seasons, suggesting it is a reliable, year-round fishing ground that may require specific management focus. The eastern side of the island exhibits the most dramatic seasonal shift. During Kaskazi, the entire eastern reef edge and shelf are heavily utilized. In contrast, during Kuzi, this effort almost entirely evaporates, likely due to the high energy and wind exposure of the Southeast Monsoon.

Breaking down the effort per gear shows a different distribution in effort (Figure 2.32).

- High-Intensity & Widespread Gears

- Hand Line: The most prevalent gear type in Pemba East. It shows a nearly continuous band of effort along the entire eastern reef edge and extends significantly into the northern

Figure 2.32: Distribution of total effort for individual gears.

section of the MPA. It likely represents the highest number of individual fishers.

- Ring Net: Shows concentrated, high-intensity "hotspots," particularly in the northern reaches of the MPA and just outside the western boundary. The effort is more clustered than hand lines, suggesting targeted fishing for pelagic or schooling species
 - Longline: Similar to hand lines but with a slightly more offshore distribution. It maintains a consistent presence across the northern and eastern shelf, indicating a broad spatial impact.
- Target-Specific & Localized Gears
 - Spear: Effort is notably concentrated in the northern tip and a few specific "pockets" along the eastern coast. Given the nature of spearfishing, these hotspots likely correspond to high-complexity reef habitats or specific coral structures within the MPA.
 - Trap: Displays very localized clusters, particularly around the northern boundary and specific eastern points. This suggests that trap placement is highly dependent on specific benthic habitats.
 - Low-Intensity/Minimal Footprint Gears
 - Shark Net: Within the Pemba East MPA, this gear shows the lowest overall effort. The activity is very sparse and primarily restricted to the far northern and eastern-most edges of the boundary.
 - Gill Net: Similar to shark nets, gill net effort is relatively low and fragmented within the eastern MPA compared to the western side of the island.

Figure 2.33: Difference between total fishing effort per gear in Kuzi and Kaskazi. Positive values indicate higher effort during Kuzi, while negative values indicate higher effort during Kaskazi.

Seasonality of fishing effort

Seasonality of fishing effort for the total effort is shown in Figure 2.33, showing how seasonality is the primary driver of fishing spatial footprint. Because the eastern side of Pemba is a windward coast, the shift from the Kaskazi (NE Monsoon) to the Kuzi (SE Monsoon) creates a massive change in accessibility.

1. Eastern Pemba Changes: For almost every gear type—specifically Hand line, Longline, Ring net, and Trap—there is a near-total withdrawal from the eastern shelf during the Kuzi season. Hand line & Longline in Kaskazi, cover the entire eastern edge of the MPA. In Kuzi, the effort is concentrated almost entirely on the sheltered northern tip or the western side of the island. Ring nets show the most binary shift. They are highly active in the northern and eastern MPA sections during Kaskazi but virtually disappear from those zones in Kuzi.
2. Northern Pemba Stability: The northwestern corner of your proposed MPA (the area near the "bend" in the red dashed line) is the only region that maintains consistent, high-intensity pressure across both seasons. Spear & Hand line remain concentrated in that northern area year-round. This northern zone is likely the most ecologically stressed due to a lack of "natural" seasonal

rest, making it a high-priority candidate for stricter protection levels within the MPA design.

3. Gear-Specific Anomalies

- Spearfishing: Interestingly, spearfishing effort remains relatively stable in the north but shifts slightly along the eastern coast. Since freedivers are less affected by deep swells than small boats but more affected by surface surge and visibility, their "pockets" of effort change less drastically than net or line fishers.
- Gill net & Shark net: These remain low-intensity throughout the year in the East, suggesting that, regardless of the season, these gears are not the primary drivers of pressure in this specific MPA project area.

Fishing grounds statistics

Here we present some statistics on the size and types of fishing grounds. These statistics help in understanding fisheries and fishers' behavior. In Figure 2.34, we show histograms depicting the area of fishing grounds per various fishing gears. The vast majority of fishing grounds are small in scale, but some gear fish on large ones. In particular, *longlines*, *shark nets*, and *ring nets* are the gears covering the largest areas, as shown by the longer tail in the semi-log histogram. On the other side, *gill nets*, *spears*, and *traps* show the smallest size of fishing grounds, with almost all fishing grounds having a size below 25 km².

Figure 2.34: Histogram of the size of the fishing grounds by gear.

In Figure 2.35, we then looked at how communities access the fishing grounds. In particular, we looked at the number of fishing grounds that communities access and the number of communities that access each fishing ground. The first figure then shows that most of the communities have access to about 30 fishing grounds each. There are notable exceptions to this, with some communities that fish almost 100 fishing grounds.

Figure 2.35: Histogram of the number of fishing grounds per community (left) and communities per ground (right).

2.5.4 Conclusions

Fishery pattern mapping provides an effective, participatory approach for gathering detailed information on fishing effort and spatial use from local communities. Fishing grounds are generally defined consistently across groups, and discrepancies can be resolved through on-site validation with community representatives. The methodology for calculating total fishing effort reduces the influence of outliers and inaccuracies by consolidating individual contributions into a comprehensive map of all recorded fishing areas. Aligning fishing-gear definitions with frame-survey data is essential to accurately scale each gear's contribution to user numbers.

Importantly, fishery pattern mapping provides insights into fishery characteristics that are difficult to obtain from conventional frame surveys or vessel-tracking technologies. The method can be integrated with landing-site data, including catches of reef fish, sharks, and rays, enabling spatial linkage between catch and fishing grounds. This integration supports more precise assessments of fishing effort, productivity, and critical habitats such as nurseries and hotspots for sharks and rays.

These efforts are already underway in selected locations where WCS collects data, and future studies will explore the full potential of this methodology to inform spatial prioritization models, enhance marine conservation planning, and support sustainable fisheries management. This work demonstrated a cost-effective and rapid method for mapping fishing grounds that accurately covers large areas. Potential uses of these datasets include studying fisheries, particularly for generating data to support spatial prioritization models. Future efforts will focus on integrating FPM data with ecological spatial layers and other relevant data sources to identify optimal locations for FRZs. Additionally, further applications of this extensive dataset for fishery management and research will be explored.

Final Remarks

Empirical Foundation for the Pemba East MCA

The baseline datasets for the Pemba East MCA confirm a significant spatial overlap between high-biodiversity corridors and intensive artisanal extraction. The integration of landing site monitoring and stereo-BRUV surveys has successfully characterized the region as a critical hub within the Western Indian Ocean elasmobranch network. Specifically, the high frequency of Endangered and Vulnerable taxa—dominated by *Carcharhinus falciformis* and *Sphyrna lewini*—establishes a scientific justification for the region’s designation as an Important Shark and Ray Area (ISRA). The demographic profile of these landings, characterized by a near-total dominance of immature individuals, identifies the Pemba East seascape as a functional nursery ground where fishing pressure is currently exerted on the most vulnerable life stages.

Socioeconomically, the “social license” for formal management is robust, with 90% of the population endorsing the efficacy of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). This support is driven by a widespread internal recognition of resource depletion, as 87% of respondents have documented significant catch declines attributed to overfishing and climatic shifts. However, the Basic Necessities Survey (BNS) indicates that the success of the MCA is fundamentally linked to the mitigation of local poverty. The data demonstrates that conservation outcomes are statistically tied to household stability, requiring that management interventions address the documented deficits in healthcare, education, and infrastructure to ensure long-term compliance and reduced dependency on nearshore extraction.

Management Recommendations for the General Management Plan (GMP)

1. Spatial Zoning for Life-History Protection

The GMP should prioritize spatial zoning that protects the reproductive potential of elasmobranch and bony fish stocks. Based on the concentration of juvenile Silky sharks and Blue-spotted maskrays recorded at sites such as Kojani and Msuka, the GMP should implement No-Take Zones (NTZs) or seasonal closures specifically aligned with the pupping and recruitment periods of these species. This spatial strategy is essential to reducing the high juvenile mortality rates currently observed and ensuring that individuals survive to reach reproductive maturity, thereby facilitating the “spillover effect” anticipated by the community. The plan should also include support for NTZs in areas with high-coral cover, which represent a small fraction of the total reef areas, to support larval recruitment

in neighbouring reefs, thus ensuring more resilient reef fisheries.

2. Technical Gear Regulations and Transitions

Management must address the disproportionate impact of non-selective gears identified in the landing data. Longlines and Jarife (large-mesh gillnets) are the primary drivers of elasmobranch mortality, with Jarife alone accounting for over 65% of ray landings. The GMP should mandate a phased transition toward more selective fishing methods and the adoption of bycatch-reduction technologies, such as circle hooks and the prohibition of wire traces in longlining. These technical shifts are necessary to decouple general fisheries production from the incidental mortality of Endangered, Threatened, and Protected (ETP) species. These interventions should be accompanied by support to phase out the use of destructive gears like beach seines and dragnets (ring-nets used in shallow waters).

3. Co-Management and Enforcement Frameworks

To address the community's demand for increased enforcement—expressed by 63.5% of respondents—the GMP should formalize a co-management framework that integrates Shehia Fisheries Committees patrols with state enforcement agencies. This community-led enforcement should be supported by the continued deployment of digital monitoring tools like SMART and KoboCollect to ensure that patrol effort is data-driven and spatially optimized. Continuous monitoring will allow for the calculation of Catch Per Unit Effort (CPUE) as a primary metric for assessing management efficacy.

4. Livelihood Diversification and Poverty Mitigation

To mitigate the economic impact of spatial restrictions, the GMP should incorporate land-based livelihood diversification programs—specifically in the agricultural and poultry sectors—as identified by the community's stated preferences for alternative income streams. By prioritizing infrastructure development and basic service delivery alongside marine enforcement, stakeholders can reduce the "poverty trap" that drives over-extraction. Aligning ecological protection with these socioeconomic aspirations can generate a viable path to establishing a self-sustaining management cycle that secures both biodiversity and local food security in Pemba East.

List of Figures

1.1	Survey team interviewing community member in Pemba	14
1.2	Perception of reduction in catch levels in Pemba East.	19
1.3	Perception of coral reef degradation in Pemba East.	20
1.4	On the left panel, a measure of hazard calculated as the percentage of respondents who selected a given Threat. On the right panel, a measure of Vulnerability calculated how often a threat was selected as the one most affecting the respondent’s livelihood.	26
1.5	On the left panel, a measure of hazard calculated as the percentage of respondents who selected a given Threat. In the right panel, a measure of Vulnerability was calculated as the frequency with which a threat was selected as the one most affecting the respondent’s livelihood.	27
1.6	Climate Risk Score for Pemba and Tanga, where the same analysis was conducted.	28
2.1	Comparison of the sampling of common benthic assessment methods. Currently, there are no methods to effectively sample the scales between 10 and 100 km ²	31
2.2	Metal tripod mounted with a camera that was used to capture benthic images.	32
2.3	Sampling design for the Benthic Ecological Survey. On the left panel, the grid of sampling stations along the Pemba East North and South coastline. In the right panel, a photo of the GoPro camera mounted on a metal tripod is used to capture images of the benthos.	33
2.4	Results of the BES survey in northern Pemba are shown, with larger circles indicating higher percentage coverage. The proposed boundaries are shown in purple. Top left – hard coral cover. Top right – seagrass cover. Bottom middle – rubble cover.	36
2.5	Results of the BES survey in southern Pemba are shown, with larger circles indicating higher percentage coverage. The proposed boundaries are shown in purple. Top left – hard coral cover. Top right – seagrass cover. Bottom middle – rubble cover.	38
2.6	Distribution of benthic classes across the entire survey area. The pie chart shows the percentage of the total area covered by each substrate class, while the bar chart provides a more detailed breakdown of the relative abundance of each class.	40
2.7	Histograms of the distribution of points per quadrant.	41
2.8	2D histograms showing the dependence of Hard Coral and Seagrass on depth.	41
2.9	Maps showing the location of the BES stations (black dots) the areas with live hard coral (blue dots), and the areas with coral cover according to the three satellite layers we are considering in this comparison.	43

2.10	WCS scuba diver completing a LIT transect for benthic cover.	46
2.11	Post-bleaching Hard Coral percentages for the surveyed sites in the north (top) and south (bottom).	49
2.12	Recruitment surveys for Mshame inner and outer reef in the northern Pemba.	51
2.13	Results from fish biomass surveys in northern (top) and southern (bottom) Pemba.	52
2.14	Sea urchins statistics for the Northern (top) and Southern (bottom) sites.	53
2.15	Circular sampling plot design. Credit Rashid Ismail, WIOMN.	56
2.16	Inventory plots distribution for Pemba study sites. Left Pemba north Msuka bay. Right Pemba Middle East.	58
2.17	Stem diameter distribution in Pemba study area.	61
2.18	Deployment of a BRUV unit in Latham Island, Zanzibar. Photo credit: Dr. Ryan Daly/ORI.	70
2.19	Sampling effort for monitoring of bony fishes across the four monitored sites in Pemba East.	71
2.20	Species composition of shark and ray landings, along with their IUCN Red List status.	72
2.21	Effort by type of vessel for monitoring of bony fishes across the four monitored sites in Pemba East.	73
2.22	Catch Per Unit Effort (CPUE) for monitoring of bony fishes across the four monitored sites in Pemba East.	74
2.23	Effort data for shark and ray landings across the four monitored sites in Pemba East.	74
2.24	Species composition of shark and ray landings, along with their IUCN Red List status.	75
2.25	Sex ratios and maturity status of sharks and rays in the landings.	76
2.26	Gear used to catch sharks and rays and whether animals are targetted or not.	77
2.27	BRUV deployment location in Pemba East.	78
2.28	BRUV deployment depth in Pemba East.	78
2.29	Fishery mapping operations with fishers in Misali Island.	80
2.30	Example of the various shapefiles for a specific fishing ground. The boundaries of the same fishing ground vary as reported by fishers from different villages and fishing gears. The resulting fishing effort is the sum of the contributions of all fishing grounds.	82
2.31	Total fishing effort for all gear and seasons.	84
2.32	Distribution of total effort for individual gears.	85
2.33	Difference between total fishing effort per gear in Kuzi and Kaskazi. Positive values indicate higher effort during Kuzi, while negative values indicate higher effort during Kaskazi.	87
2.34	Histogram of the size of the fishing grounds by gear.	89
2.35	Histogram of the number of fishing grounds per community (left) and communities per ground (right).	90

List of Tables

1.1	Demographic data across various villages.	16
1.2	Distribution of Livelihood Activities	17
1.3	Comparison of Marine vs. Non-Marine Livelihoods by Ranking	18
1.4	Potential Livelihood Activities Respondents Wish to Pursue	19
1.5	Summary of Potential Livelihood Interests (Marine vs. Non-Marine)	20
1.6	Community Support for Conservation and MPA Management	21
1.7	Preferred management measure from the socioeconomic survey respondents	22
1.8	BNS survey scores per item, separated by north and southeast Pemba	22
1.9	Climate Risk Assessment Variables and Survey Questions	25
1.10	Climate Risk Score for each sampled village. Scores are also disaggregated for fishers and non-fishers.	29
2.1	CoralNet Benthic Categories and Functional Groups	35
2.2	Coverage in area and percentage of the coral reef and seagrass areas.	39
2.3	Sites surveyed in the East of Pemba, going from North to South.	47
2.4	Description of inventory plots, including GPS position and altitude.	57
2.6	Allometric models recommended for estimation of AGB ($kg\ tree^{-1}$) and BGB ($kg\ tree^{-1}$) for mangroves of Tanzania [Njana et al., 2018].	59
2.7	Percentage mangrove species composition and distribution at the study sites. Source: Field data collected in 2024. Note: - indicates absence of the species at the site.	61
2.8	Average DBH, Density, and Basal Area per Site and Species	62
2.9	Biomass and Carbon Stock by Site and Species	63
2.10	Stump Density and Distribution by Shehia	64
2.11	Sapling Counts and Regeneration Density	65
2.12	Number of units of gear in each area	83

Bibliography

Robert C. Allen. Absolute poverty: When necessity displaces desire. *American Economic Review*, 107 (12):3690–3721, 2017. ISSN 00028282. doi: 10.1257/aer.20161080.

Faustinato Behivoke, Marie Pierre Etienne, Jérôme Guitton, Roddy Michel Randriatsara, Eulalie Ranaivoson, and Marc Léopold. Estimating fishing effort in small-scale fisheries using GPS tracking data and random forests. *Ecological Indicators*, 123, 2021. ISSN 1470160X. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.107321.

J.O. Bosire, F. Dahdouh-Guebas, J.G. Kairo, and N. Koedam. Colonization of non-planted mangrove species into restored mangrove stands in Gazi Bay, Kenya. *Aquatic Botany*, 76(4):267–279, August 2003a. ISSN 03043770. doi: 10.1016/S0304-3770(03)00054-8. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0304377003000548>.

J.O. Bosire, F. Dahdouh-Guebas, J.G. Kairo, and N. Koedam. Colonization of non-planted mangrove species into restored mangrove stands in Gazi Bay, Kenya. *Aquatic Botany*, 76(4):267–279, August 2003b. ISSN 03043770. doi: 10.1016/S0304-3770(03)00054-8. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0304377003000548>.

Sébastien Desbureaux, Julia Girard, Alicia Dalongeville, Rodolphe Devillers, David Mouillot, Narriman Jiddawi, Loic Sanchez, Laure Velez, Laetitia Mathon, and Antoine Leblois. The long-term impacts of Marine Protected Areas on fish catch and socioeconomic development in Tanzania. *Conservation Letters*, 2024.

D Detoef, M Wieland, and D Wilke. Guide 2.0 to the Modified Basic Necessities Survey: Why and How to Conduct Digital-Based BNS in Conservation Landscapes. Technical report, Wildlife Conservation Society, 2020. URL <https://library.wcs.org/Scientific-Research/Research-Publications/Publications-Library/ctl/view/mid/40093/pubid/DMX383850000.aspx>.

Gabriela Navarrete Forero, Sara Miñarro, Tobias Karl Mildenerger, Annette Breckwoldt, Sudirman, and Hauke Reuter. Participatory boat tracking reveals spatial fishing patterns in an Indonesian artisanal fishery. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 4(DEC):1–12, 2017. ISSN 22967745. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2017.00409.

Kauffman J.B. and Donato D. Protocols for the measurement, monitoring and reporting of structure, biomass and carbon stocks in mangrove forests. Technical report, Center for International Forestry Research (CIFOR), 2012. URL <http://www.cifor.org/library/3749/protocols-for-the-measurement-monitoring-and-reporting-of-structure-biomass-and-carbon-stocks-in-m>

- J.G. Kairo, F. Dahdouh-Guebas, J. Bosire, and N. Koedam. Restoration and management of mangrove systems — a lesson for and from the East African region. *South African Journal of Botany*, 67(3): 383–389, September 2001. ISSN 02546299. doi: 10.1016/S0254-6299(15)31153-4. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0254629915311534>.
- Binita Kc, J. M. Shepherd, Anthony W. King, and Cassandra Johnson Gaither. Multi-hazard climate risk projections for the United States. *Natural Hazards*, 105(2):1963–1976, January 2021. ISSN 0921-030X, 1573-0840. doi: 10.1007/s11069-020-04385-y. URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11069-020-04385-y>.
- Emma V. Kennedy, Chris M. Roelfsema, Mitchell B. Lyons, Eva M. Kovacs, Rodney Borrego-Acevedo, Meredith Roe, Stuart R. Phinn, Kirk Larsen, Nicholas J. Murray, Doddy Yuwono, Jeremy Wolff, and Paul Tudman. Reef Cover, a coral reef classification for global habitat mapping from remote sensing. *Scientific Data*, 8(1):1–20, 2021a. ISSN 20524463. doi: 10.1038/s41597-021-00958-z.
- Emma V. Kennedy, Chris M. Roelfsema, Mitchell B. Lyons, Eva M. Kovacs, Rodney Borrego-Acevedo, Meredith Roe, Stuart R. Phinn, Kirk Larsen, Nicholas J. Murray, Doddy Yuwono, Jeremy Wolff, and Paul Tudman. Reef Cover, a coral reef classification for global habitat mapping from remote sensing. *Scientific Data*, 8(1):196, August 2021b. ISSN 2052-4463. doi: 10.1038/s41597-021-00958-z. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-021-00958-z>.
- T R McClanahan. Fisheries yields and species declines in coral reefs. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17(4):044023, April 2022. ISSN 1748-9326. doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/ac5bb4. URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/ac5bb4>.
- Tim R. McClanahan, Nicholas A.J. Graham, M. Aaron MacNeil, Nyawira A. Muthiga, Joshua E. Cinner, J. Henrich Bruggemann, and Shaun K. Wilson. Critical thresholds and tangible targets for ecosystem-based management of coral reef fisheries. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 108(41):17230–17233, October 2011. ISSN 00278424. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1106861108.
- Timothy R. McClanahan and Maxwell Kodia Azali. Improving sustainable yield estimates for tropical reef fisheries. *Fish and Fisheries*, 21(4):683–699, 2020. ISSN 14672979. doi: 10.1111/faf.12454.
- Timothy R. McClanahan, Alan M. Friedlander, Nicholas A.J. Graham, Pascale Chabanet, and J. Henrich Bruggemann. Variability in coral reef fish baseline and benchmark biomass in the central and western Indian Ocean provinces. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 31(1): 28–42, 2021. ISSN 10990755. doi: 10.1002/aqc.3448.
- P. J. Mumby, E. P. Green, A. J. Edwards, and C. D. Clark. Coral reef habitat mapping: how much detail can remote sensing provide? *Marine Biology*, 130(2):193–202, December 1997. ISSN 0025-3162, 1432-1793. doi: 10.1007/s002270050238. URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s002270050238>.
- Mohamad Natsir, Toni Ruchimat, Siska Agustina, and Irfan Yulianto. Application of global positioning system tracker to detect the fishing ground location and effective effort in artisanal fishery. *Sensors and Materials*, 31(3):803–814, 2019. ISSN 09144935. doi: 10.18494/SAM.2019.2238.

Marco A Njana, Eliakimu Zahabu, and Rogers E Malimbwi. Carbon stocks and productivity of mangrove forests in Tanzania. *Southern Forests: a Journal of Forest Science*, 80(3):217–232, July 2018. ISSN 2070-2620, 2070-2639. doi: 10.2989/20702620.2017.1334314. URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.2989/20702620.2017.1334314>.

Benjamin D. Rubin, Paul D. Manion, and Don Faber-Langendoen. Diameter distributions and structural sustainability in forests. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 222(1-3):427–438, February 2006. ISSN 03781127. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2005.10.049. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0378112705006729>.

UNEP-WCMC, WorldFish, WRI, and TNC. Global distribution of coral reefs, compiled from multiple sources including the Millennium Coral Reef Mapping Project. Version 4.1, updated by UNEP-WCMC. Includes contributions from IMaRS-USF and IRD (2005), IMaRS-USF (2005) and Spalding et al. (2001), 2021.